

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 501-600 / 100 entries

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In that case

それなら

Sore nara

In that case

Variants

- それなら
In that case
- それなら行こう^い
In that case, let's go
- それなら大丈夫^{だいじょうぶ}
Then it's fine
- それならやめよう
In that case, let's stop
- それなら、そうしよう
Then let's do that

Adjusted Expression

そうであれば、そのようにしましょう。

If that is the case, let's do that.

Example

A 「今日は雨^{きょう}み^{あめ}たいだよ」 B 「それなら、家^{いえ}で映画^{えいが}を見^みよう」

A: Looks like it's going to rain today. B: In that case, let's watch a movie at home.

Notes

"Sore nara" is used when the speaker receives the other person's statement or the current situation and shifts their judgment or action accordingly. In this example, B hears that it looks like rain and changes the plan to watching a movie at home. Learners may analyze it as a conditional form built from "sore" plus "nara," but in everyday conversation it often works as an immediate response close to "then" or "in that case," leading smoothly to the next judgment or proposal.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

conditional shift suggestion agreement switching judgment

receiving the other person's statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language conditional expression suggestion expression

judgment shift response expression casual speech

As soon as

...とすぐ、

...to sugu,

as soon as ...

Variants

- ...とすぐ
as soon as ...
- ...とすぐに
right after ...
- ...てすぐに
immediately after ...
- ...とたん
the moment ...
- ...と同時に^{どうじ}
at the same time as ...

Adjusted Expression

...すると、すぐに...

as soon as ... happened, ...

Example

げんかん^{げんかん} あ ^{ねこ}猫が^と飛びかかってきた。

As soon as I opened the door, the cat jumped at me.

Notes

"...to sugu" is a linking expression used when one event happens almost immediately after another. In this example, the cat jumps at the speaker right after the door is opened. Here, "to" is not simply a conditional marker; it creates the sense that the second event arises immediately from the first. Compared with "totan," it may sound less strongly unexpected, but it clearly shows that the two events are closely connected in time.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

immediacy

event chain

temporal connection

unexpected event

quick reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

linking expression

time expression

event chain

immediacy

unexpected event

spoken language

I had no choice but to...

しかなくて

shika nakute

I had no choice but to...

Variants

- 行くしかなくて
I had no choice but to go
- 待つしかなくて
I had no choice but to wait
- 謝るしかなくて
I had no choice but to apologize

Adjusted Expression

～する以外いがいに方法ほうほうはなくて

there was no other option but to ...

Example

A 「どうして遅おくれたの？」 B 「電車でんしゃが止とまって、歩あるくしかなくて...」

A: Why were you late? B: The train stopped, so I had no choice but to walk...

Notes

"Shika nakute" is an immediate grammar expression used to say there was no other option. It often appears in excuses or explanations, and can

also trail off to leave the situation implicit. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "...suru hoka nakute."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

limitation

excuse

inevitability

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

constraint

If you had been watching, you should have known

...てたら、...はずで

...tetara, ...hazu de

if you had been ..., you should have ...

Variants

- ^み見てたら、^わ分かるはずで
If you had seen it, you should have known
- ^き聞いてたら、^し知ってるはずで
If you had heard it, you would know
- やってたら、^き気づくはずで
If you had tried it, you should have noticed
- ^よ読んでたら、^わ分かるはずで
If you had read it, you would understand
- そこにいたら、^き気づくはずで
If you had been there, you should have noticed

Adjusted Expression

...ていたなら、...はずだったのですが。

If you had been ..., then you should have

Example

A 「え？そんなことあったの？」 B 「それは^み見てたら、^わ分かるはずで...」

A: Huh? That happened? B: If you had been watching, you should have noticed...

Notes

"...tetara, ...hazu de" is used when the speaker judges that the listener should have known or noticed something if they had been watching, listening, or experiencing it. In this example, B says "mitetara, wakaru hazu de...", implying that A should have noticed if they had been watching. Ending with "de" leaves the utterance unfinished, softening the assertion while still conveying dissatisfaction or mild reproach.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting grounds soft assertion implication dissatisfaction avoiding full assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language emotion presenting grounds
implicational expression incomplete sentence judgment expression

How does it end up like that?

なんでそうなるの？

Nande sou naru no?

How does it end up like that?

Variants

- なんでそうなるの？
How does it end up like that?
- なんでそうなる？
Why does it end up like that?
- どうしてそうなるの？
How come it turns out that way?
- なんでそんなことになるの？
Why does that happen?
- どうしてそんなことになったの？
How did it come to that?

Adjusted Expression

どうしてそのようなことになるのですか？

Why does it turn out that way?

Example

A 「パソコンを直なおそうとしたら、もっと壊こわれた」 B 「えっ、なんでそうなるの？」

A: I tried to fix my computer, but it broke even more. B: What? How does it end up like that?

Notes

"Nande sou naru no?" is an emotional question used in response to an unexpected or hard-to-accept result. In this example, B reacts with surprise and incredulity to the fact that the computer broke even more when A tried to fix it. It is not just a neutral request for a reason; it also conveys the feeling that the result does not make sense and needs an explanation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise discontent incredulity demanding an explanation

reaction to an unexpected result

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language question expression emotional expression

non-acceptance demanding explanation reaction expression

..., though

...なんだけどね

...nan da kedo ne

..., though

Variants

- 行きたかったんだけどね
I wanted to go, though...
- 頑張ったんだけどね
I tried hard, though...
- いい試合だったんだけどね
It was a good game, though...
- そう思ったんだけどね
That's what I thought, though...

Adjusted Expression

...なのですが

...however,

Example

A 「^{しあい}試合、^ま負けちゃったね？」 B 「いい^{ぶれい}プレイはあったんだけどね...」

A: We lost the game, huh? B: There were some good plays, though...

Notes

"...nan da kedo ne" is used when the speaker trails off and leaves part of the meaning unstated, inviting the listener to infer the rest. In this example, the speaker accepts the fact that they lost, but also implies that the game cannot be dismissed so simply because there were good plays. The final "ne" softens the tone and adds a nuance of seeking empathy or shared understanding.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation

trailing off

seeking empathy

leaving something unsaid

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

implication

empathy

follow-up chain

I never thought that...

...とはおも思わなかった

...to wa omowanakatta

I never thought that...

Variants

- か勝てるとはおも思わなかった

I never thought we could win

- きみ あ君に会えるとはおも思わなかった

I never thought I would see you

- こんなにじかん時間がかかるとはおも思わなかった

I never thought it would take this long

- ここまでこ来られるとはおも思わなかった

I never thought we could come this far

- まさか、こうなるとはおも思わなかった

I never thought it would turn out like this

Adjusted Expression

...とはおも思いませんでした。

I did not expect that...

Example

A 「ゆうしょう優勝できたね！」 B 「うん、まさかか勝てるとはおも思わなかった」

A: We won the championship! B: Yeah, I never thought we could win.

Notes

"...to wa omowanakatta" is used when what actually happened went beyond the speaker's expectations. In this example, B responds to the championship win by saying "kateru to wa omowanakatta," expressing surprise and deep feeling. The "to wa" highlights the unexpected content and gives the utterance a retrospective tone. It can be used for both positive and negative outcomes, but in either case it conveys that reality was not what the speaker had expected.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

unexpectedness surprise retrospection deep feeling unexpected outcome

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language unexpectedness emotional expression

retrospective expression unexpected outcome casual speech

If it's alright with you...

もし、よかったら、

Moshi, yokattara,

If it's alright with you...

Variants

- もし、よかったら、^{いっしょ}一緒に^い行きませんか？
If it's alright with you, would you come with me?
- もし、よかったら、^{つか}使^つってください
If it's alright with you, please use it
- もし、よかったら、^み見^みてみて
If it's alright with you, have a look
- よかったら、あとで^{いっしょ}一緒に^いやらない？
If you'd like, why don't we do it together later?
- もしよかったら、どうぞ
If you'd like, please go ahead

Adjusted Expression

もしよろしければ、

If you do not mind, ...

Example

A 「^{しゅくだい}宿題、むずかしかった？」 B 「うん。もし、よかったら、あとで^{いっしょ}一緒にやらない？」

A: Was the homework difficult? B: Yeah. If you'd like, why don't we do it together later?

Notes

"Moshi, yokattara," is used before making a suggestion or invitation while showing respect for the listener's situation or feelings. In this example, B places "moshi, yokattara" before inviting A to do the homework together, leaving room for A to decline. Placed before the main expression, it functions as a lead-in chain that helps the following invitation arise softly. In more formal contexts, it is expressed as "moshi yoroshikereba."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

tentative suggestion

consideration

invitation

restraint

leaving room for the listener to choose

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

polite

suggestion expression

invitation expression

consideration expression

lead-in chain

How about coming?

こ
来ない？

Konai?

How about coming?

Variants

- 来ない？
How about coming?
- 行かない？
How about going?
- 食べない？
How about eating?
- 飲まない？
How about having a drink?
- 一緒に行かない？
Do you want to go together?

Adjusted Expression

き
来ませんか？

Would you like to come?

Example

A 「お昼、どうする？」 B 「ラーメン食べに行かない？」

A: What should we do for lunch? B: How about going for ramen?

Notes

"V-nai?" is grammatically a negative question, but in friendly conversation it often works as a casual invitation. In this example, B says "ikanai?" to suggest going for ramen together. The negative form makes the invitation softer than a command or strong proposal, leaving room for the listener to decline. In more formal situations, forms such as "ikimasen ka?" or "kimasen ka?" are used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

invitation

suggestion

closeness

joint action

light prompting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

invitation expression

suggestion expression

negative question

joint action

casual speech

I managed to...

なんとか

Nantoka

somehow / managed to

Variants

- なんとか
somehow
- なんとか^の乗り^こ越えた
I managed to get through it somehow
- なんとか^{そつぎょう}卒業できた
I somehow managed to graduate
- なんとか^い生き^の延びた
I somehow survived
- なんとか^ま間^あに合った
I managed to make it in time

Adjusted Expression

かろうじて^の乗り^こ越えることができました。

I barely managed to get through it.

Example

A 「^{たいへん}大変だったね」 B 「うん、なんとか、^の乗り^こ越えたよ」

A: That must have been tough. B: Yeah, I managed to get through it somehow.

Notes

"Nantoka" is used when the speaker did not solve a difficult situation with ease, but somehow managed to get through it. In this example, B says "nantoka, norikoeta," expressing relief that they got through the difficulty, without first explaining exactly how. It is an immediate expression that shares the result and the feeling of relief while leaving the means unspecified.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

overcoming hardship

relief

barely succeeding

not specifying the means

sharing the outcome

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

overcoming expression

relief expression

barely managing

sharing the outcome

casual speech

I'm telling you...

...だって(ば)

...datteba

I'm telling you...

Variants

- ほんとう 本当だって
It really is, I'm telling you
- ほんとう 本当だってば
I'm telling you, it's true
- い 行ったんだってば
I went, I'm telling you
- ちが 違うんだって
I'm telling you, that's not it
- できるんだってば
I'm telling you, I can do it

Adjusted Expression

ほんとう 本当にそうです。

It really is true.

Example

A 「ほんとにできるの？」 B 「できるんだってば！」

A: Can you really do it? B: I'm telling you, I can!

Notes

"...datteba" is used when the listener does not believe, accept, or fully take in what the speaker has already said. In this example, B has said that they can do it, but A still doubts it, so B says "dekiru n datteba!" to insist. This is different from the quotative "datte" meaning "they say." Here, the speaker is pushing their own claim toward the listener and trying to make it accepted. Because the emotion is strong, it can also carry irritation or frustration.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis

insistence

frustration

wanting the listener to accept it

repeated assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emphasis expression

insistence

emotional expression

frustration

reaction expression

If it had..., then...

...たなら、 ...

...ta nara, ...

If it had..., then...

Variants

- 行^いけたなら、会^あえたのに

If I had been able to go, I could have seen you

- 知^しっていたなら、準^{じゅん}備^びした

If I had known, I would have prepared

- 一^{いっ}緒^{しょ}だったなら、楽^{たの}しかった

If we had been together, it would have been fun

Adjusted Expression

もし...たならば、...したでしょう。

If it had..., then it would have....

Example

勇^{ゆう}気^きがあったなら、言^いえたのに...

If I had had the courage, I could have said it...

Notes

"...ta nara, ..." presents a counterfactual condition and often conveys regret or disappointment. It imagines a condition that was not actually true and suggests another possible outcome. Ending with "...noni" leaves

the feeling unfinished and emotionally lingering. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "moshi ...ta naraba, ...shita deshou."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hypothetical regret emotional lingering

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language hypothetical emotion

counterfactual condition incomplete sentence

Oh, so that's how it was

そうだったんだ

Sou datta n da

Oh, so that's how it was

Variants

- そうだったんですね
Oh, I see, that's how it was
- そうだったのか
So that's what happened
- そうだったんだね
So that's how it was, huh

Adjusted Expression

そうだったのですね。

I see, that was the case.

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼、^{てんこう}転校してたんだよ。」 B 「そうだったんだ！」

A: He had transferred schools. B: Oh, so that's how it was!

Notes

"Sou datta n da" is an immediate grammar expression used when new information brings about understanding or acceptance. Although it uses the past form "datta," it conveys the present realization of "I see" or "So that's what happened." It functions as a fixed expression of realization

rather than a literal past-tense statement. In formal contexts, it becomes "sou datta no desu ne."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acceptance

understanding

realization

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

acceptance

realization

Taking the trouble to...

わざわざ

Wazawaza

taking the trouble to / going out of one's way

Variants

- わざわざ^き来てくれてありがとう
Thank you for taking the trouble to come
- わざわざ^い言わなくてもいい
You didn't have to say it
- わざわざ^も持ってきてくれた
You went out of your way to bring it

Adjusted Expression

とく
特に

especially / particularly

Example

A 「わざわざ^{とど}届けてくれたんだ」 B 「いいえ、ついでですから」

A: You went out of your way to deliver this. B: No, it was on the way.

Notes

"Wazawaza" is used when the speaker recognizes that an action involved special effort or trouble. Depending on context, it can express gratitude or criticism. In "wazawaza kite kurete arigatou," it expresses gratitude,

while in "wazawaza iwanakute mo ii," it can express criticism or displeasure. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "tokubetsu ni" (especially) or "aete" (intentionally).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude

criticism

emphasis

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

gratitude

criticism

emphasis

Fairly / relatively

わりと

Warito

fairly / relatively

Variants

- わりと^{やす}安い
fairly cheap
- わりと^{しず}静か
relatively quiet
- わりとよくできている
rather well done

Adjusted Expression

^{ひかくてき}
比較的

comparatively / relatively

Example

A 「この店、^{みせ たか}高い？」 B 「ううん、わりと^{やす}安いよ。」

A: Is this place expensive? B: No, it's fairly cheap.

Notes

"Warito" is a casual evaluative expression used when something feels less extreme than expected, or better than expected in degree. In this example, B answers that the place is "warito yasui," meaning it is fairly cheap. Rather than strong praise, it gives a soft comparative judgment: it

is cheap relative to expectation. In formal contexts, it is replaced with "hikakuteki" (comparatively).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

unexpectedness

colloquial softening

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

unexpectedness

degree expression

That's it

それがそうなんだよ

Sore ga sou nan da yo

That's it

Variants

- それがそうなんだよ

That's it

- それがそうなんだよね

That's exactly it

- まさにそこなんだよ

That's the point

- そこがそうなんだよ

That's what I mean

Adjusted Expression

まさにそれが^{じじっ}事実なのです。

That is exactly the case.

Example

A 「それって、まさか、^{とうきゅう}東急じゃないよね？」 B 「それがそうなんだよ」

A: Wait, you don't mean Tokyu, do you? B: That's it. It is Tokyu.

Notes

"Sore ga sou nan da yo" is used when the speaker accepts the other person's surprised confirmation and says that it is exactly the case. In this example, A asks, "Wait, you don't mean Tokyu, do you?" and B replies, "Sore ga sou nan da yo." Although "sore" and "sou" are abstract, they become meaningful through the immediately preceding utterance. The phrase confirms the listener's realization or suspicion as correct. Depending on the situation, it can be close to "Exactly," "That's it," or "That's the point." In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "That is exactly the case."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acceptance

empathy

pointing out an issue

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

acceptance

implication

Little by little / It's about time

ぼちぼち

Bochibochoi

little by little / it's about time

Variants

- ぼちぼち^い行こか
Shall we get going?
- 仕事^{しごと}はぼちぼちやっています
I'm working little by little
- 景気^{けいき}はぼちぼちやな
The economy is so-so

Adjusted Expression

^{すこ}少しずつ / そろそろ

gradually / it's about time

Example

A 「最近^{さいきん}どう？」 B 「まあ、ぼちぼちかな」

A: How are things lately? B: Well, so-so, I guess.

Notes

"Bochibochoi" is a colloquial expression originally associated with Kansai dialect, but it is now widely understood. Depending on context, it can mean "little by little," "so-so," or "it's about time." In this example, "maa,

bochibochi kana" gives a modest answer meaning that things are neither especially good nor bad. In an expression like "bochibochi ikoka," it can signal that it is about time to get going. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "sukoshi zutsu" (little by little), "sorosoro" (it's about time), or "maa maa desu" (so-so).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gradual progress

signal for it's time

modest evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

softening

progress

modest evaluation

If you like / If anything

なんなら

Nannara

if you like / if anything

Variants

- なんなら^{てっだ}手伝いますよ
If you like, I can help
- なんなら^{かえ}帰ってもいい
If anything, you can go home
- なんならやめてもいいよ
If necessary, you can quit

Adjusted Expression

もしよければ / ^{ひつよう}必要なら

if you like / if necessary

Example

A 「明日、^{あす}荷物^{にもつ}多いんだ」 B 「なんなら^{くるま}車^{おく}で送るよ」

A: I'll have a lot of luggage tomorrow. B: If you like, I can give you a ride.

Notes

"Nannara" is used to gently offer a suggestion or option to the listener. In this example, B says "nannara kuruma de okuru yo," offering to give A a ride if needed. Depending on context, it can also have a sense close to "rather" or "if anything." It is difficult to translate directly, but it is often

used when the speaker responds to the listener's situation and offers a slightly more involved option. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "moshi yokereba" (if you like) or "hitsuyou nara" (if necessary).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

suggestion

emphasis

soft contrast

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

suggestion

implication

By all means / No matter what

なんとしても

Nantoshitemo

by all means / no matter what

Variants

- なんとしても^{せいこう}成功させたい
I want to make it succeed by all means
- なんとしても^い行かなければならない
I must go no matter what
- なんとしても^{まもぬ}守り抜く
I will protect it at all costs

Adjusted Expression

どのような^{しゅだん}手段を取っても

by any means / whatever the means

Example

A 「無理^{むり}じゃない？」 B 「なんとしてもやり^と遂げる！」

A: Isn't it impossible? B: I'll get it done no matter what!

Notes

"Nantoshitemo" expresses strong determination to accomplish something by any means. In this example, B says "nantoshitemo yaritogeru," showing the will to finish it despite the difficulty. It is often used for

strong positive resolve, but depending on context it can also convey obligation or urgency. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "by any means" or "certainly."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

strong will

determination

inevitability

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emphasis

will

determination

Normally / Usually

いつもなら

Itsumo nara

normally / usually

Variants

- いつもなら寝^ねている時間^{じかん}
Normally I'd be asleep at this time
- いつもなら怒^{おこ}るところ
Normally I'd get angry
- いつもなら行^いかない店^{みせ}
Normally I wouldn't go to this shop

Adjusted Expression

通常^{つうじょう}であれば

under normal circumstances

Example

A 「今日^{きょう}は遅^{おそ}いね」 B 「いつもならもう帰^{かえ}ってるんだけど」

A: You're late today. B: Normally I'd already be home.

Notes

"Itsumo nara" brings up one's usual habit or baseline to contrast it with the current situation. In this example, B says "itsumo nara mou kaetteru n da kedo," explaining that today's situation is different from usual. By

bringing in the usual baseline immediately, the speaker can naturally convey surprise, discomfort, or explanation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "tsuujou de areba" (under normal circumstances).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

baseline

comparison

situation difference

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

habit

comparison

situation explanation

Right? / Isn't it?

だよね

Da yo ne

right? / isn't it?

Variants

- いい^{てんき}天気だよね

It's nice weather, right?

- 難^{むずか}しかったよね

That was difficult, wasn't it?

- 楽^{たの}しかったよね

It was fun, wasn't it?

Adjusted Expression

そうですよね。

That's true.

Example

A 「ふつう、こんなことしないよ！」 B 「だよね！」

A: Normally, nobody would do such a thing! B: Exactly!

Notes

"Da yo ne" is used to show immediate agreement or empathy with what the other person has said. It is common in casual speech, and it can stand alone to mean something like "Exactly" or "I feel the same way." In this example, B responds briefly with "da yo ne!" and shares A's surprise or

frustration. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sou desu yo ne" or "sou desu ne."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

empathy

conversational link

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

empathy

confirmation

agreement expression

Busted!

ば れ
バレた？

Bareta?

Busted?

Variants

- ^{かく}隠してたけど^{ば れ}バレた？

I tried to hide it, but you noticed?

- ^{うそ}嘘ついたの^{ば れ}バレた？

Did you catch my lie?

- ^{きも}気持ち^{ば れ}バレた？

Did you notice my feelings?

Adjusted Expression

^き気づかれましたか？

Did you notice?

Example

A 「^{ほんとう}本当は^い行きたくなかったんでしょ？」 B 「^{ば れ}バレた？」

A: You actually didn't want to go, right? B: Busted?

Notes

"Bareta?" is used when the speaker's true feelings or secret have been noticed by someone else. In this example, B's reluctance to go has been noticed by A, and B responds lightly with "bareta?" It is often used with

embarrassment or playfulness rather than as a serious confession. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "Did you notice?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

true feelings revealed

secret exposed

playful admission

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

playful

emotion

being found out

Oops, I... / I ended up...

ちゃった

Chatta

oops, I... / I ended up...

Variants

- ^ね寝ちゃった
I fell asleep, oops
- ^{わす}忘れちゃった
I forgot, oops
- ^た食べちゃった
I ate it, oops

Adjusted Expression

...してしまった

ended up doing...

Example

A 「宿題しゅくだいどうした？」 B 「忘れわすちゃった！」

A: What about the homework? B: I forgot, oops!

Notes

"Chatta" is the colloquial contraction of "...shite shimatta." It expresses a mistake or unintended action with a light, immediate tone. In this example, B says "wasurechatta!" to say that they forgot the homework. Rather than deep regret, it often carries a sense of having slipped up,

embarrassment, or mild apology. In formal contexts, it is expressed as "...shite shimaimashita."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

mistake

unexpected action

mild regret

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

contraction

emotion

unintentional action

Well, you see...

うーん、それはね

Uun, sore wa ne

well, you see...

Variants

- うーん、それはね、ちょっと^{ちが}違うよ
Well, you see, that's a bit different
- うーん、それはね、説明^{せつめい}が難^{むずか}しいんだ
Well, you see, it's hard to explain
- うーん、それはね、^わ分からない
Well, you see, I don't know

Adjusted Expression

それについてはですね。

Regarding that, you see...

Example

A 「^いなんで行かなかったの？」 B 「うーん、それはね、ちょっと...」

A: Why didn't you go? B: Well, you see, it's a bit...

Notes

"Uun, sore wa ne" is a prefatory phrase used while thinking, signaling that an explanation will follow. "Uun" marks the speaker's thinking time, and "sore wa ne" takes up the listener's question while avoiding an immediate direct answer. It conveys hesitation or consideration and

creates a natural pause in conversation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sore ni tsuite wa desu ne" (regarding that..).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

thinking

preface

soft explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

preface

hesitation

lead-in chain

You're good at it! / Not bad!

できるねえ

Dekiru nee

You're good at it! / Not bad!

Variants

- よくできるねえ
You can really do it!
- そんなこともできるねえ
You can even do that!
- ^{ひとり}一人でできるねえ
You can do it all by yourself!

Adjusted Expression

^{じょうず}上手ですね / よくできますね。

You're skilled. / You do it well.

Example

A 「^み見て、この^え絵、どう？」 B 「できるねえ！」

A: Look at this picture. What do you think? B: Not bad!

Notes

"Dekiru nee" is an immediate expression of praise or admiration for someone's ability or action. It is casual and often used in close relationships, with a tone of surprise or shared feeling. Depending on tone, it can be straightforward praise or a slightly playful evaluation. In

formal contexts, it can be replaced with "jouzu desu ne" (you're skilled) or "yoku dekimasu ne" (you do it well).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

admiration

praise

surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

exclamation

What else can you do?

ほか なに
他、何、できる？

Hoka, nani, dekiru?

What else can you do?

Variants

- ^{ほか}他、できることある？
Is there anything else you can do?
- ^{ほか}他、^{なに}何かできたりする？
Can you do anything else?
- ^{ほか}他には？
Anything else?

Adjusted Expression

^{ほか}他に^{なに}何ができますか？

What else can you do?

Example

A 「^{えいご}英語できるんだ？」 B 「うん」 A 「^{ほか}他、^{なに}何、できる？」

A: You speak English? B: Yeah. A: What else can you do?

Notes

"Hoka, nani, dekiru?" is an immediate, casual way to ask what else someone can do, with particles and some structure omitted. Rather than being only a request for information, it also continues the topic after the

listener's previous answer. Grammatically, it can be expanded to "Hoka ni nani ga dekimasu ka?", but in spoken Japanese the shorter form "Hoka, nani, dekiru?" sounds natural and easy to understand.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking

follow-up

exploratory

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

ellipsis

flexible word order

Do you know?

し
知ってる？

Shitteru?

Do you know?

Variants

- これ^し知ってる？
Do you know this?
- あの^{ひと}人^し知ってる？
Do you know that person?
- その^{はなし}話^し知ってる？
Do you know that story?

Adjusted Expression

^{ぞん}ご存じですか。

Do you happen to know?

Example

A 「ねえ、これ^し知ってる？」 B 「うん、^{まえ}前^みに見たよ」

A: Hey, do you know this? B: Yeah, I saw it before.

Notes

"Shitteru?" is a casual expression used to check immediately whether the listener knows something. In this example, A says "nee, kore shitteru?" to confirm the listener's knowledge while introducing a topic. It is not only

a check of knowledge, but also a way to see whether the speaker and listener can share the same topic. In formal situations, it can be replaced with "gozonji desu ka."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation topic introduction shared awareness

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language confirmation shared knowledge

topic introduction

Lately / These days

ここんとこ

Kokon toko

lately / these days

Variants

- ここんとこ^{いそが}忙しくて
I've been busy lately
- ここんとこ^あ会ってないね
We haven't met lately
- ここんとこずっと^{ねむ}眠い
I've been feeling sleepy these days

Adjusted Expression

このところ

recently / these days

Example

A 「元^{げん}気？」 B 「いや、ここんとこ^{つか}ちょっと疲れてて」

A: How are you? B: Hmm, I've been kind of tired lately.

Notes

"Kokon toko" is a colloquial contraction of "kono tokoro" or "koko saikin," used to refer to a vaguely recent span of time. In this example, B says "kokon toko chotto tsukaretete," lightly explaining that they have been tired lately. The contracted form gives the expression a friendly, casual

tone and makes it useful as a topic opener. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "kono tokoro" or "saikin."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

recent status

topic opener

context sharing

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

ellipsis

temporal expression

Muttering to oneself

...つと

...tto

muttering to oneself

Variants

- ^{むずか}難しいなつと

Hmm, that's kind of hard

- ^{こわ}怖いなつと

Hmm, that's kind of scary

- じゃ、がんばるぞつと

All right, let's do this

- さて、やるかつと

Okay, let's get started

Adjusted Expression

...しようと思^{おも}って

I thought I would...

Example

A 「もう^じ3時！」 B 「じゃ、もう^{すこ}少し、がんばるぞつと」

A: It's already 3 o'clock! B: Well, I guess I'll keep going a little longer.

Notes

"...tto" is used to let a short inner utterance come out lightly, almost like muttering to oneself. In this example, B says "ganbaru zo tto," using the expression to push themselves to keep going a little longer. It can bring out an inner evaluation, as in "muzukashii natto" or "kawai natto," but it can also work as a small self-directed prompt, as in "ja, ganbaru zo tto" or "sate, yaru ka tto." Although it resembles the quotative "to," here it functions less as an explanatory quotation and more as an immediate externalization of inner speech.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

muttering

immediate judgment

externalizing inner speech

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

muttering

inner speech

evaluation

self-starting

Ah, so that's your move.

そう、きたか

sou, kita ka

So that's how you're playing it.

Variants

- そうきたか
Ah, so that's your move.
- おお、そうきたか
So that's how you're playing it.
- そう来るとは
I didn't see that coming.

Adjusted Expression

そう来きましたか

I see, so that was your move.

Example

A 「で、そこでまさかの謝罪しゃざいぶん文ですよ」 B 「...そう、きたか。」

A: And then, out of nowhere, he sent an apology letter. B: ...Ah, so that's his move.

Notes

"Sou, kita ka" is used when reacting to an unexpected move or turn of events. It expresses not only surprise but also a quick uptake of the other's move, as if saying, "Ah, so that's the way you're playing it." It often

carries a sense of impressed acceptance rather than simple astonishment. In more formal contexts, it can be rephrased as "Sou kimashita ka."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

uptake

instant evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction

exclamation

Nothing

なに
何も

Nani mo

Nothing

Variants

- なに
何もない

There is nothing

- なに
何もなかった

There was nothing

- なに
何もいらぬ

I don't need anything

Adjusted Expression

とく
特にありません。

Nothing in particular.

Example

A 「どうしたの？」 B 「^{なに}何も。」

A: What's wrong? B: Nothing.

Notes

"Nani mo" is an immediate grammar expression used as a short response to a question. In this example, by saying only "nani mo," the speaker implicitly means "nothing" or "nothing in particular." By not completing

the sentence, the speaker can leave some ambiguity, including the feeling that they do not want to explain further or are leaving something unsaid. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "tokuni arimasen" (nothing in particular).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

response

negation

ambiguity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

response

ellipsis

ambiguity

negation

Come on, do it

...てよ

...te yo

Come on, do it

Variants

- ^た食べてよ
Eat it!
- ^み見てよ
Look at it!
- なんとかしてよ
Do something about it!
- やってよ
Come on, do it!
- ^み見てきてよ
Go check it out, will you?

Adjusted Expression

^み見てきてください。

Could you go and have a look, please?

Example

A 「^{そと}外、^み見てきて」 B 「えー、^み見てきてよ〜」

A: Go check outside. B: Ugh, you go check it out!

Notes

"...te yo" is a spoken expression formed by adding the sentence-final particle "yo" to the te-form of a verb. It is used with close others when making an emotionally colored request or demand. In this example, A says "go check outside," and B replies "mite kite yo," pushing the request back to A. It can sound friendly or playful, but depending on the situation it can also carry pressure or dissatisfaction. In formal contexts, it is replaced by "...te kudasai."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

request demand emotion pressure familiarity

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language sentence-final particle emotion

request expression demand expression

For ... / Considering ...

にしちやあ

Ni shichaa

for ... / considering ...

Variants

- ^{わか}若いにしちやあ
for being young
- ^{やす}安いにしちやあ
for being cheap
- ^{うま}上手いにしちやあ
for being good

Adjusted Expression

～にしては

for ... / considering ...

Example

A 「彼、^{かれ}若いよね」 B 「うん、^{わか}若いにしちやあ、^お落ち^つ着いてるよね」

A: He's young, right? B: Yeah, for being young, he's pretty composed.

Notes

"Ni shichaa" is a casual spoken form of "...ni shite wa," used to express evaluation or surprise by comparing something with a certain standard or expectation. In this example, the speaker evaluates him as composed compared with what might be expected from someone young. It is used

in casual conversation, and in formal contexts it can be replaced with
"...ni shite wa."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

comparison

surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

comparison

surprise

evaluation expression

Well, that's that / So be it

じゃ、それで。

Ja, sore de.

Well, that's that / So be it

Variants

- じゃ、そうするよ
Well, I'll do that
- じゃ、それでいいよ
Well, that's fine
- じゃ、決^きまりだね
Well, it's decided then

Adjusted Expression

それでよろしいです。

That will be fine.

Example

A 「出^{しゅっぱつ}発、明日^{あした}に延期^{えんき}しようか」 B 「うん、じゃ、それで」

A: So, shall we postpone the departure to tomorrow? B: Yeah, let's do that.

Notes

"Ja, sore de" is used to quickly reach a conclusion and accept a proposal or option in conversation. In this example, B accepts the suggestion to postpone the departure until tomorrow by saying "ja, sore de." It is

common in casual conversation and lightly confirms the decision. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sore de yoroshii desu" (That will be fine).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

decision

conclusion

acceptance

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

conclusion

acceptance

Even if you don't go so far as to say...

とは言いわないまでも、

To wa iwanai made mo,

even if you don't go so far as to say...

Variants

- 好すきとは言いわないまでも

Even if you don't go so far as to say you like it

- 嫌きらいとは言いわないまでも

Even if you don't go so far as to say you hate it

- 得とく意いとは言いわないまでも

Even if you don't go so far as to say you're good at it

Adjusted Expression

とは言いいませんが、

I would not say that, but ...

Example

A 「彼かれ、天てん才さいだよね」 B 「うーん、天てん才さいとは言いわないまでも、優すぐれてるよね」

A: He's a genius, right? B: Hmm, I wouldn't go so far as to say he's a genius, but he's certainly exceptional.

Notes

"To wa iwanai made mo," is a euphemistic expression used to partially agree with someone's opinion without fully endorsing it. In this example,

B does not go so far as to call him a genius, but does acknowledge that he is exceptional. It is common in written language and suitable for formal contexts, although it may sound somewhat stiff in casual conversation. It can be replaced with "to wa iimasen ga" (I would not say that, but ...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

modest expression indirect agreement preface

Tags EN

immediate grammar written language euphemistic expression preface

So it is tasty, huh?

おいしいんかい

Oishii n kai

So it is tasty, huh?

Variants

- ^{たか}高いんかい

So it is expensive, huh?

- ^{やす}安いんかい

So it is cheap, huh?

- ^{むずか}難しいんかい

So it is difficult, huh?

Adjusted Expression

^{けっきょく}結局、おいしいのですね。

So it is tasty after all.

Example

A 「この料理、^{りょうり}美味しいよ」 B 「おいしいんかい！」

A: This dish is tasty. B: So it is tasty after all!

Notes

"N kai" is a casual form related to "no kai," used to express surprise or confirmation in response to what someone has said or to the situation. It is especially common as a Kansai-style retort, reacting to something

unexpected or to a conclusion that feels slightly off from the flow of the conversation. In this example, B says "oishii n kai!" with a sense of surprise or playful retort. In formal contexts, it can be expressed as "So it is tasty after all."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

confirmation

emotional expression

retort

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

confirmation

retort

Kansai dialect

Because I wanted to...

たくて

Takute

because I wanted to...

Variants

- ^た食べたくて
because I wanted to eat
- ^い行きたくて
because I wanted to go
- ^{はな}話したくて
because I wanted to talk

Adjusted Expression

～たいので

because I want to ...

Example

A 「^{やさい}野菜だけは、^{ざいりょう}いい材料^{つか}を使いたくて」 B 「へえ、そうなんだ」

A: I wanted to use good ingredients, at least for the vegetables. B: Oh, I see.

Notes

"Takute" combines the "tai" form of a verb with the connective particle "te," presenting desire as a reason or motivation. In this example, the speaker says "ii zairyō o tsukaitakute," softly explaining why they made

that choice or why they feel that way. When it ends the utterance, it trails off without fully completing the reason, leaving the listener to receive the motivation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "...tai node" (because I want to ...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

desire

motivation

emotional expression

giving a reason

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

desire

motivation

trailing off

Something like ... / Kind of like ...

よوناもの

You na mono

something like ... / kind of like ...

Variants

- ^{ゆめ}夢のよوناもの
something like a dream
- ^{ゆめ}夢のよوناもん
kind of like a dream
- ^{えいが}映画のよوناもの
something like a movie
- おとぎ話^{ばなし}のよوناもの
something like a fairy tale

Adjusted Expression

のよوناもの

something like ...

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼の^{はなし}話、^{ゆめ}夢のよوناもんだよね」 B 「うん、^{しん}信じられないよね」

A: His story is kind of like a dream, right? B: Yeah, it's unbelievable.

Notes

"You na mono" or the more casual "you na mon" is used to describe something metaphorically or to present it as close to something without stating it directly. In this example, "yume no you na mon" conveys that his story feels so unbelievable that it is almost like a dream. "You na mono" sounds more explanatory, while "you na mon" is more casual and spoken. It is an immediate expression that softly conveys an impression or feeling without defining it too precisely.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

metaphor

example

vague expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

metaphor

vagueness

Even if we put it aside

お
置いといたとして

Oitoita toshite

even if we put it aside

Variants

- お置いといたとして
even if we put it aside
- 実現性^{じつげんせい}は置いといたとして
even if we put aside the feasibility
- 細かい^{こま}ことは置いといたとして
even if we put aside the details
- それは置いといたとして
putting that aside

Adjusted Expression

わき お
脇に置いたとしても

even if we put it aside

Example

A 「実現性^{じつげんせい}は置いといたとして、面白い^{おもしろ}話^{はなし}だよね」 B 「うん、確かに^{たし}」

A: Even if we put aside the feasibility, it's an interesting idea, right? B: Yeah, certainly.

Notes

"Oitoita toshite" is a casual form of "oite oita toshite," used when the speaker temporarily sets an issue aside and continues the discussion from another angle. In this example, A sets aside the question of feasibility and evaluates the idea itself as interesting. The expression does not erase the issue; it temporarily removes it as something not to be dealt with at that moment, allowing another perspective to be considered. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "even if we put it aside" or "even if we temporarily exclude it."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hypothesis

condition

thought experiment

temporarily setting aside an issue

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

hypothesis

condition

organizing the point

That's true, but...

そうなんだけどね

Sou nan da kedo ne

That's true, but...

Variants

- いいんだけどね
That's fine, but...
- ^わ分かるんだけどね
I understand, but...
- ^{たす}助かるんだけどね
That helps, but...

Adjusted Expression

そうなんですけどね、

That's true, but...

Example

A 「彼、^{かれ}優しいよやさね」 B 「うん、そうなんだけどね、^{やさ}優しすぎるんだよ」

A: He's kind, right? B: Yeah, that's true, but he's too kind.

Notes

"Sou nan da kedo ne" is used when the speaker first accepts what the other person has said and then adds an objection or supplement. In this example, B agrees that he is kind, but continues with another evaluation: he is too kind. The "dakedo ne" allows the speaker to move to a different

view without directly rejecting the listener's statement. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sou desu ga" or "sou na no desu ga."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

agreement

objection

supplement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

agreement

objection

supplement

I see / Is that so?

そうなんだ

Sou nan da

I see / Is that so?

Variants

- ほんと、そうなんだ
Is that really so?
- へえ、そうなんだ
Oh, is that so?
- なるほど、そうなんだ
I see, so that's how it is

Adjusted Expression

そうなんですか。

I see. Is that so?

Example

A 「彼、^{かれ}結婚^{けっこん}するんだって」 B 「へえ、そうなんだ」

A: I heard he's getting married. B: Oh, is that so?

Notes

"Sou nan da" is a colloquial expression used to show immediate understanding or surprise after hearing what someone has said. In this example, B receives the new information that he is getting married and responds with "hee, sou nan da." The speaker is not merely giving

information; they also have a wish to share it. "Sou nan da" receives both the information and the act of wanting to tell it. In contrast, responses such as "dakara, nani," "dakara, nan da," or "dakara, nan da tte iu no" do not receive the other person's utterance and instead block the conversation. A considerate speaker would not use such expressions; even when they do not wish to continue the topic, they can receive it lightly with "hee, sou nan da" and let the conversation pass. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sou nan desu ka" or "sou desu ka."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

- understanding
- surprise
- empathy

Tags EN

- immediate grammar
- spoken language
- understanding
- surprise
- backchannel

That may be so, but...

それはそれとして

Sore wa sore to shite

That may be so, but...

Variants

- 問題は問題として
The problem is the problem, but...
- 事実は事実として
The fact is the fact, but...
- 意見は意見として
The opinion is the opinion, but...

Adjusted Expression

それは別の問題だとして、...

That may be a separate matter, but...

Example

A 「彼、優しいよね」 B 「うん、それはそれとして、仕事は厳しいよね」

A: He's kind, right? B: Yeah, that may be so, but he is strict about work.

Notes

"Sore wa sore to shite" is used when the speaker first acknowledges someone's opinion or a fact and then moves to another perspective or topic. In this example, B accepts that he is kind, but shifts to another

evaluation: he is strict about work. The expression allows the speaker to move on by separating the points without directly rejecting the previous statement. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sore wa betsu no mondai da to shite" (treating that as a separate matter).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

contrast

topic shift

supplement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

contrast

topic shift

organizing the point

I totally agree

だいさんせい
大賛成

Dai sansei

I totally agree

Variants

だいさんせい
● 大賛成

I totally agree

だいはんたい
● 大反対

I strongly disagree

だいかんげい
● 大歓迎

I warmly welcome it

だいしじ
● 大支持

I strongly support it

Adjusted Expression

おお さんせい
大いに賛成です。

I strongly agree.

Example

A 「じゃ、ビール、飲みに行こう！」 B 「うん、だいさんせい、大賛成！」

A: So, let's go for a beer! B: Yeah, I totally agree!

Notes

"Dai sansei" is used to strongly agree with or approve of someone's opinion or proposal. In this example, B immediately responds with "dai sansei!", warmly accepting the suggestion. Compared with "sansei," it has more energy and can be used in conversation as a lively expression of agreement. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "ooi ni sansei desu" (I strongly agree).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

agreement

approval

emphasis

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

agreement

approval

emphasis

I definitely want to...

ぜひ、そうしたいですよ

Zehi sou shitai desu yo

I definitely want to...

Variants

- ぜひ^い行きたいですよ
I definitely want to go
- ぜひ^あ会いたいですよ
I really want to meet
- ぜひ^{さんか}参加したいですよ
I definitely want to participate
- ぜひ、そうしたいです
I would definitely like to do that

Adjusted Expression

ぜひ、そのようにいたしたい^{おも}と思います。

I would definitely like to do that.

Example

A 「^{じかい}次回は、もっと^{じかん}時間をかけて、^{ぎろん}議論しませんか？」 B 「ええ、ぜひ、そうしたいですよ！」

A: Next time, shall we take more time for discussion? B: Yes, I definitely want to!

Notes

"Zehi sou shitai desu yo" is used to show strong desire or enthusiasm in response to someone's suggestion. In this example, B responds positively to the suggestion of taking more time for discussion by saying "zehi sou shitai desu yo." The word "zehi" makes the response more than simple agreement; it shows that the speaker also strongly wants to do it. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "zehi ...tai to omoimasu" (I definitely want to...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

strong desire

enthusiasm

proactiveness

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

desire

emphasis

positive response

Is it over already?

あれ、もう^お終わり？

Are, mou owari?

Is it over already?

Variants

- あれ、もう^お終わり？

Is it over already?

- えっ、もう^お終わり？

Wait, is it over already?

- もう^お終わり？

Is that it already?

- あれ、もう^お終わったの？

Is it already finished?

Adjusted Expression

もう^お終わりですか？

Is it over already?

Example

A 「これで、おしまい。面白^{おもしろ}かったね」 B 「あれ、もう^お終わり？」

A: That's it. It was fun, right? B: Wait, is it over already?

Notes

"Are, mou owari?" is a colloquial expression used when something ends earlier than the speaker expected, showing immediate surprise or confirmation. In this example, B responds to A's "That's it" by saying "Are, mou owari?" The opening "are" conveys a small mismatch with the speaker's expectation and a sense of surprise. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "mou owari desu ka?" (Is it over already?).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

confirmation

emotional expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

confirmation

surprise

You mean...?

っていうことは？

Tte iu koto wa?

You mean...?

Variants

- つまり？

In other words?

- ^{よう}要するに？

To sum up?

- ということは？

So, are you saying...?

Adjusted Expression

つまり、...ということですか。

In other words, does that mean...?

Example

A 「明日、^{あした}雨^{あめ}だって」 B 「っていうことは、^{ちゅうし}中止？」

A: They say it's going to rain tomorrow. B: You mean it's canceled?

Notes

"Tte iu koto wa?" is used when the speaker receives what someone has said and checks the meaning or result that follows from it. In this example, B hears that it will rain tomorrow and asks, "tte iu koto wa, chuushi?", confirming the likely result. It is not just a paraphrase; it is an

immediate confirmation expression that draws a possible conclusion from the other person's utterance. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "In other words, does that mean...?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

understanding

surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

confirmation

understanding

inference

So what does that mean?

ってどうなの？

Tte dou nano?

So what does that mean?

Variants

- それってどうなの？
So what does that mean?
- どうなの？
How should I take that?
- それで大丈夫だいじょうぶなの？
Is that okay?

Adjusted Expression

それはどういうことですか？

What does that mean?

Example

A 「明日、あした 雨あめだって」 B 「ってどうなの？ちゅうし 中止？」

A: They say it's going to rain tomorrow. B: So what does that mean? Is it canceled?

Notes

"Tte dou nano?" is used when the speaker receives what someone has said and asks how that situation should be understood or judged. In this example, B hears that it will rain tomorrow and asks whether that means

the event will be canceled. While No.546 "tte iu koto wa?" draws out a possible conclusion, "tte dou nano?" asks how the information should be interpreted or handled. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "What does that mean?" or "How should we understand that?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

checking judgment

understanding

uncertainty

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

confirmation

understanding

checking judgment

No way! / It can't be!

そんなあ！

Sonnaa!

No way! / It can't be!

Variants

- ^{うそ}嘘でしょ！
You're kidding!
- まさか！
No way!
- ^{しん}信じられない！
I can't believe it!

Adjusted Expression

それはおかしいですね。

That does not seem right.

Example

A 「今日から、また元の値段に戻るんだって」 B 「そんなあ！」

A: I heard the price is going back to the original from today. B: No way!

Notes

"Sonnaa!" is a colloquial expression used to immediately show surprise, dissatisfaction, or denial in response to unexpected or hard-to-accept news. In this example, B reacts with "sonnaa!" after hearing that the price is going back to the original. It is natural in casual conversation, but

in formal situations, expressing dissatisfaction immediately can sound rude. In such cases, it can be replaced with "That does not seem right."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

denial

emotional expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

surprise

complaint

I can't keep up / I can't follow

ついてけない

Tsuitekenai

I can't keep up / I can't follow

Variants

- あたま 頭がついてけない

My head can't keep up

- はなし 話についてけない

I can't follow the conversation

- へんか 変化についてけない

I can't keep up with the changes

Adjusted Expression

ついていきません。

I can't keep up.

Example

A 「さいきん 最近、あたら 新しいぎじゅつ 技術がつぎつぎ 次々に出てくるよね」 B 「ほんとう うん、本当についてけないよ」

A: New technologies are coming out one after another these days, right?

B: Yeah, I really can't keep up.

Notes

"Tsuitekenai" is a casual contraction of "tsuite ikenai," used when the speaker feels unable to keep up with a conversation, situation, or rapid

change. In this example, B says "hontou ni tsuitekenai yo" in response to new technologies appearing one after another. It does not simply mean not understanding; it also conveys the feeling that one's mind cannot keep up with the speed or amount of change. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "tsuite ikemasen" (I can't keep up).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confusion

lack of understanding

emotional expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

confusion

contracted form

I get dragged into ... / I end up getting pulled along

ひ
引きずられちゃう

Hikizurarechau

I get dragged into ... / I end up getting pulled along

Variants

- かんじょう ひ感情に引きずられちゃう
I get dragged along by my emotions
- かこ ひ過去に引きずられちゃう
I end up getting stuck in the past
- じょうきょう ひ状況に引きずられちゃう
I get pulled along by the situation

Adjusted Expression

とらわれてしまいます。

I end up being caught up in it.

Example

A 「かれ い かた ひ彼の言い方に引きずられちゃうよね」 B 「ほんとう れいせい かんがうん、本当に。冷静に考えると
ぜんぜんさんせい全然賛成できないんだけどね」

A: You get pulled along by his way of speaking, right? B: Yeah, really.
When I think about it calmly, I can't agree with it at all.

Notes

"Hikizurarechau" is a casual contraction of "hikizurarete shimau," meaning that the speaker gets pulled along or caught up by emotions, past events, the atmosphere of a situation, or someone's way of speaking, even though they do not intend to. In this example, A says that they get pulled along by his way of speaking and find it hard to judge calmly. The "chau" ending adds the feeling that it happens unintentionally and somewhat troublingly. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "eikyou sarete shimaimasu" (I end up being influenced) or "torawarete shimaimasu" (I end up being caught up in it).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

self-reflection

situation explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

self-reflection

being influenced

Lately / These days

さいきん
ここ最近

Koko saikin

lately / these days

Variants

- ^{さいきんいそが}ここ最近忙しい
Lately I've been busy
- ^{さいきんさむ}ここ最近寒い
These days it's cold
- ^{さいきんつか}ここ最近疲れる
Lately I get tired

Adjusted Expression

さいきん
最近

recently / lately

Example

A 「^{さいきん}最近、^{いそが}忙しい？」 B 「うん、ここ^{さいきん}最近は^{ほんとう}本当に^{いそが}忙しいよ」

A: Have you been busy lately? B: Yeah, I've been really busy these days.

Notes

"Koko saikin" is formed by adding "koko" before "saikin," and it is used when the speaker has in mind a recent stretch of time connected to the present. In this example, B says "koko saikin wa hontou ni isogashii yo,"

expressing that they have been very busy in the recent period leading up to now. However, it is difficult to explain the addition of "koko" as a general productive rule. Expressions like "soko saikin" or "koko chotto mae" are not freely formed in the same way, so "koko saikin" is best learned as a fixed expression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

recent updates

topic introduction

emotional expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

recent updates

topic introduction

I'm lucky / I'm fortunate

ついてる

Tsuiteru

I'm lucky / I'm fortunate

Variants

- ^{きょう}今日はついてる
I'm lucky today
- なんかついてる
I feel lucky somehow
- ^{ほんとう}本当についてる
I'm really lucky
- ^{うん}運がついてる
Luck is on my side
- ツイてる
I'm lucky

Adjusted Expression

^{うん}運がいいです。

I'm lucky.

Example

A 「^{たから}宝くじ、^あ当たったんだって？」 B 「^{うん}、^{ほんとう}本当についてるよ」

A: I heard you won the lottery? B: Yeah, I'm really lucky.

Notes

"Tsuiiteru" is a colloquial expression used when the speaker feels lucky or feels that something unexpectedly good has happened. In this example, B responds to winning the lottery by saying "hontou ni tsuiiteru yo," expressing joy and a sense of good luck. Compared with simply explaining that one is lucky, it conveys the immediate feeling of being lucky in the moment. Conversely, when someone feels unlucky, they may use "tsuitenai."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude

joy

self-affirmation

recognizing good luck

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

gratitude

joy

luck expression

I mean, ... / More like, ...

というかね、 ...

To iu ka ne, ...

I mean, ... / More like, ...

Variants

- というかね、 ...

I mean, ...

- なんていうかね、 ...

How should I put it, ...

- しょうじき い正直言うとね、 ...

To be honest, ...

Adjusted Expression

せいかく い正確に言うと、 ...

More precisely, ...

Example

A 「彼^{かれ}って、本^{ほん}当^{とう}に優^{やさ}しいよね」 B 「うん、というかね、優^{やさ}しすぎるんだよ」

A: He's really kind, right? B: Yeah, I mean, he's too kind.

Notes

"To iu ka ne, ..." is a spoken expression used when the speaker receives what the other person has said and then shifts it slightly toward another view or a more honest feeling. In this example, B is not denying that he is kind, but moves to a slightly different evaluation: he is too kind. "To iu ka

ne" is not just a paraphrase; it lets the speaker accept the previous view while moving toward what they really want to say. For this reason, what follows can sometimes be somewhat negative or critical.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation supplement topic shift showing one's real feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language explanation supplement honest feeling

shifting evaluation

The reason is...

なぜかつつと、...

Naze kattsuu to, ...

The reason is...

Variants

- なぜかつつと、...

The reason is, ...

- なぜかつつと、...

The thing is, ...

- なぜかっていうと、...

Here's why, ...

- りゆう理由はね、...

The reason is, you see, ...

- ぼいんとポイントはね、...

The point is, ...

Adjusted Expression

なぜなら、...

The reason is, ...

Example

A 「きょう今日はね、いえすぐ家かえに帰る。なぜかつつと、かのじょ彼女のたんじょうび誕生日なんだ」

A: I'm going straight home today. The reason is, it's my girlfriend's birthday.

Notes

"Naze kattsuu to, ..." is a very casual form of "naze ka to iu to," used when the speaker is about to give a reason. In this example, A first says that they are going straight home and then introduces the reason with "naze kattsuu to." In friendly conversation, "nazenara" can sound too stiff, as if the speaker were writing an essay or giving a formal explanation. "Naze kattsuu to" works as an immediate spoken lead-in that adds a reason lightly and keeps the conversation moving. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "naze ka to iu to" or "nazenara."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation

justification

emphasis

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

explanation

justification

contracted form

When you put it that way, ...

っていうとね、

Tte iu to ne,

when you put it that way, ...

Variants

- そんなこと言ったら、
If you say that, ...
- そう言くと、
When you put it that way, ...
- そう言ってしまったら、
If you say it like that, ...

Adjusted Expression

そう言ってしまうと、

When put that way, ...

Example

A 「だいたい5時間ぐらいかかる、っていうとね、すごく難しいような感じがするけど、実は、簡単」

A: When I say it takes about five hours, it sounds really difficult, but actually, it's easy.

Notes

"Tte iu to ne, ..." is a spoken expression used when the speaker continues by adjusting how their own or someone else's wording may be received. In this example, saying that it takes about five hours may make it sound difficult, but the speaker corrects that impression by adding that it is actually easy. "Tte iu to" is a casual form of "to iu to," and "ne" adds the sense of checking in with the listener while continuing the explanation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "sou itte shimaimasu to" (when put that way).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation supplement pointing out an excessive impression

adjusting how something is received

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language explanation supplement

adjusting interpretation

For about an hour

こいちじかん
小一時間ほど

Koichijikan hodo

for about an hour

Variants

- ^{こいちじかん}小一時間ほど
for about an hour
- ^{やくいちじかん}約一時間
approximately one hour
- ^{いちじかん}およそ一時間
around one hour
- ^{いちじかん}だいたい一時間
roughly one hour
- ^{いちじかんじゃく}一時間弱
a little less than an hour

Adjusted Expression

^{やくいちじかん}
約一時間

approximately one hour

Example

A 「^{かいぎ}会議は^{こいちじかん}小一時間^{ほど}で」 B 「では、またその^{ころ}頃に」

A: The meeting should take about an hour. B: Then I'll see you around that time.

Notes

"Koichijikan hodo" means about an hour, often with the sense of a little less than an hour. In this example, A gives an estimate of the meeting length by saying "koichijikan hodo." Compared with "daitai ichijikan" (about an hour), it sounds a little more formal or measured, and can softly suggest that the time is not very long. However, it is not a freely productive pattern; expressions like "ko sanjuppun hodo" are not normally formed in the same way. "Koichijikan" is best learned as a fixed expression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

time estimation explanation information provision

Tags EN

immediate grammar time expression estimation explanation

slightly formal expression

Than I thought / Than expected

おも
思ったよりね

Omotta yori ne

than I thought / than expected

Variants

- ^{よそう}予想よりね

than I expected

- ^{きたい}期待してたよりね

than I had expected

- ^{かんが}考えてたよりね

than I had thought

Adjusted Expression

^{よそう}予想よりも

than expected

Example

A 「^{はや}早く^つ着いたね」 B 「うん、^{おも}思ったよりね」

A: We arrived early, didn't we? B: Yeah, earlier than I thought.

Notes

"Omotta yori ne" is a spoken elliptical response used after a preceding utterance to compare the actual result with what the speaker expected. In this example, B responds to "We arrived early" with "omotta yori ne,"

meaning "earlier than I thought." The rest of the sentence, such as "hayakatta ne" (it was early), is left unstated, so the expression becomes stable through its chain with the immediately preceding utterance.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

comparison evaluation impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language comparison evaluation elliptical response

It doesn't go as I hoped

おも
思うように行かない

Omou you ni ikanai

It doesn't go as I hoped

Variants

- おも とお い
思い通りに行かない

It doesn't go the way I want

- よそうとお い
予想通りに行かない

It doesn't go as I expected

- きたいとお い
期待通りに行かない

It doesn't go as I hoped

Adjusted Expression

よそうとお すす
予想通りに進みません。

It is not progressing as expected.

Example

A 「じゅんちょう 順調に進んでる？」 B 「うーん、おも 思うように行かないね」

A: Is it going smoothly? B: Hmm, it isn't going the way I hoped.

Notes

"Omou you ni ikanai" is used when things do not progress as the speaker expected or hoped. In this example, B says "omou you ni ikanai ne," expressing a sense of stagnation and slight frustration. It does not simply

mean that the result is different; it suggests that the speaker wants things to move in a certain direction, but the situation is not going that way. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is not progressing as expected" or "It is not progressing as hoped."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sense of stagnation

frustration

disappointment

situation explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

stagnation

disappointment

Not as I hoped

おも
思うように(は)ね

Omou you ni wa ne

Not as I hoped

Variants

- おも どお 思い通りにはね

Not the way I wanted

- よそうどお 予想通りにはね

Not as I expected

- きたいどお 期待通りにはね

Not as I hoped

Adjusted Expression

おも すす
思うようには進んでいません。

It is not progressing as I hoped.

Example

A 「じゅんちょう すす順調に進んでる？」 B 「うーん、おも思うようにはね」

A: Is it going smoothly? B: Hmm, not as I hoped.

Notes

"Omou you ni wa ne" is an incomplete form of "omou you ni wa ikanai" (it does not go as I hoped). In this example, B says only "omou you ni wa ne," implying that things are not going smoothly or not moving in the

hoped-for direction. Ending with "ne" leaves the sentence unfinished and creates a lingering sense of stagnation or disappointment shared with the listener. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "It is not progressing as I hoped."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sense of stagnation

frustration

disappointment

trailing off

emotional lingering

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

incomplete sentence

particle-final utterance

stagnation

Just a little / Just a bit

ほんのちょっと

Hon no chotto

just a little / just a bit

Variants

- ^{すこ}少しだけ
just a little
- わずかに
slightly
- ちょっぴり
just a tiny bit
- ほんのちょっとだけ
only a little bit

Adjusted Expression

^{すこ}少しだけ

just a little

Example

A ^{さと}砂糖、^{つか}使う？ B 「ほんのちょっと」

A: Do you want some sugar? B: Just a little.

Notes

"Hon no chotto" is a colloquial expression used to show that an amount, time, distance, or degree is very small. In this example, B answers "hon no chotto," meaning that they do not want much sugar, only a little. Compared with "chotto," it gives an even smaller and more modest impression. In an expression such as "hon no chotto chigau" (just a little different), the difference may be small, but it can still feel noticeable or uncomfortable to the speaker.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

quantity expression modest expression emphasis expressing slight discomfort

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language quantity expression modest expression

degree expression

What am I supposed to do?

なに
何やんなくちゃならないんだっけ

Nani yannakucha naranai n dakke

What am I supposed to do?

Variants

- ^{なに}何をしなくちゃならないんだっけ
What do I have to do?
- ^{なに}何をやらなくちゃならないんだっけ
What was I supposed to do?
- ^{なに}何をしなければならいんだっけ
What did I need to do?

Adjusted Expression

^{なに}何をすべきだったのか、^{わす}忘れてしまいました。

I forgot what I was supposed to do.

Example

A 「^{あした}明日の^{かいぎ}会議の^{じゅんび}準備、^{なに}何やんなくちゃならないんだっけ？」 B 「^{しりょう}資料の^{いんさつ}印刷
だけじゃない？」

A: What am I supposed to do to prepare for tomorrow's meeting? B: Isn't it just printing the materials?

Notes

"Nani yannakucha naranai n dakke" is a colloquial expression used when the speaker is trying to recall what they are supposed to do. In this example, A checks what needs to be done to prepare for tomorrow's meeting. "Yannakucha" is a casual form of "yaranakute wa" (have to do), and "dakke" gives the sense of trying to remember something that has slipped from memory. It can be used either to ask someone else for confirmation or as self-talk. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "I forgot what I was supposed to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

recall

self-management

self-talk

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

confirmation

recall

self-management

self-talk

I'm fed up / I'm sick of it

うんざりする

Unzari suru

I'm fed up / I'm sick of it

Variants

- 飽^あき飽^あきする

I'm fed up

- 嫌^{いや}気が^けさす

I'm sick of it

- うんざりだ

I'm tired of it

Adjusted Expression

嫌^{いや}気が^けさします。

I am fed up with it.

Example

A 「彼の^{かれ}話、またあの^{はなし}話？」 B 「うん、本当^{ほんとう}にうんざりするよ」

A: Is he telling that story again? B: Yeah, I'm really sick of it.

Notes

"Unzari suru" is used when the speaker feels fed up because the same thing is repeated or an unpleasant situation continues. In this example, B reacts to the fact that he is telling the same story again by saying "hontou ni unzari suru yo." It does not simply mean being bored; it can also

include the feeling that the speaker no longer wants to hear it or be involved with it. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "iyake ga sashimasu" (I am fed up with it) or "I am very troubled by it."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

dissatisfaction

disgust

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

dissatisfaction

fed-up feeling

For some reason...

どうしたはずみか、 ...

Doushita hazumi ka, ...

for some reason...

Variants

- どういうわけか、 ...

For some reason, ...

- なぜか^わ分からないけど、 ...

I don't know why, but ...

- 理由^{りゆう}は^わ分からないけど、 ...

I don't know the reason, but ...

- なんだか、 ...

Somehow, ...

Adjusted Expression

明確^{めいかく}な理由^{りゆう}は^わ分かりませんが、 ...

Although the exact reason is unclear, ...

Example

どうしたはずみか、休^{やす}みなのに大^{だいがく}学^きに来てしまった。

For some reason, I ended up coming to the university even though it was a day off.

Notes

"Doushita hazumi ka, ..." is used when something happened or the speaker did something for a reason that is not clear even to the speaker. In this example, the speaker says that they somehow ended up coming to the university even though it was a day off. "Hazumi" refers to a trigger, impulse, or momentum that leads to something happening. In ordinary conversation, expressions such as "dou iu wake ka" or "naze ka wakaranai kedo" may sound more natural, but "doushita hazumi ka" gives the situation a slightly retrospective or narrative tone, suggesting both unclear reason and chance.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

unclear reason

chance

self-explanation

retrospection

Tags EN

immediate grammar

unclear reason

chance

self-explanation

slightly written style

The thing is...

っていうのも、 ...

Tte iu no mo, ...

the thing is...

Variants

- っていうのも、 ...

The thing is, ...

- というのも、 ...

The reason is, ...

- りゆう理由は、 ...

That is because ...

- なんてかっていうと、 ...

Here's why, ...

Adjusted Expression

というのも、 ...

That is because ...

Example

A 「きょう今日はもうかえ帰るよ。っていうのも、かのじょ彼女のたんじょうび誕生日なんだ」

A: I'm going home now. The thing is, it's my girlfriend's birthday.

Notes

"Tte iu no mo, ..." is a spoken expression used when the speaker adds a reason or background after already saying something. In this example, A first says "I'm going home now" and then adds the reason with "tte iu no mo": it is his girlfriend's birthday. It is not a summarizing expression like "in other words"; rather, it adds background to what has just been said. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "to iu no mo" or "nazenara" (because).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation

giving a reason

supplement

adding a reason afterward

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

explanation

giving a reason

supplement

follow-up chain

Where should we start?

どこから^ああたりますか？

Doko kara atarimasu ka?

Where should we start?

Variants

- どこから^{はじ}始めますか？
Where do we begin?
- どこから^と取りかかりますか？
Where do we get started?
- どこから^て手を^つ付けますか？
Where should we tackle first?
- どこから^ああたりましょうか？
Where shall we start looking?

Adjusted Expression

どこから^{はじ}始めますか？

Where do we begin?

Example

A 「この件、どこから^ああたりますか？」 B 「まずは資料^{しりょう}の確認^{かくにん}から」

A: Where should we start with this matter? B: Let's start by reviewing the materials.

Notes

"Doko kara atarimasu ka?" is used when starting work, investigation, or a task and asking where to begin. In this example, A says "kono ken, doko kara atarimasu ka?" to confirm the entry point for the work. "Ataru" here does not mean physically hitting something; it means to tackle, investigate, or deal with a task, document, or person involved. More general alternatives are "doko kara hajimemasu ka?" (Where do we begin?) or "doko kara te o tsukemasu ka?" (Where should we start working on it?).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

planning

starting work

checking direction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

confirmation

planning

starting work

It's going well / It's working out

うまくいってる

Umaku itteru

It's going well / It's working out

Variants

- うまくいってるよ

It's going well

- じゅんちょう すず 順調に進んでる

It's progressing smoothly

- もんだい すず 問題なく進んでる

It's progressing without problems

- かん すず いい感じで進んでる

It's moving along nicely

Adjusted Expression

じゅんちょう すず 順調に進んでいます。

It is progressing smoothly.

Example

A 「しんきかく新企画はどう？」 B 「うまくいってるよ、よていとお予定通りにすす進んでる」

A: How's the new project going? B: It's going well. It's progressing as planned.

Notes

"Umaku itteru" is a colloquial expression used to say that something is going well. In this example, B is asked about the new project and answers "umaku itteru yo," giving a reassuring status report. Compared with "junchou ni susunde iru" (it is progressing smoothly), it sounds more casual and conversational, and it can also imply that there is no need to worry. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "junchou ni susunde imasu" (It is progressing smoothly).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

status report evaluation expression of reassurance

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language status report evaluation reassurance

I have to do it

しなくっちゃ

Shinakuccha

I have to do it

Variants

- しなくっちゃ
I have to do it
- やらなくっちゃ
I have to get it done
- しなきゃ
I gotta do it
- しないと
I need to do it
- しなければならない
I must do it

Adjusted Expression

しなればなりません。

I have to do it.

Example

A 「^{しゅくだい}宿題は？」 B 「うん、^{いま}今からしなくっちゃ」

A: What about your homework? B: Yeah, I have to do it now.

Notes

"Shinakuccha" is a casual spoken form related to "shinakereba naranai" or "shinakute wa ikenai," used when the speaker needs to do something. In this example, B is asked about their homework and answers "ima kara shinakuccha," confirming what they need to do from now. Rather than a strong external command, it often feels like a self-prompt that helps the speaker start acting. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "shinakereba narimasen" (I have to do it).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

obligation

necessity

self-prompting

starting action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

obligation

necessity

self-prompting

contracted form

To be restless / To be fidgety

そわそわする

Sowasowa suru

to be restless / to be fidgety

Variants

- ^お ^つ 落ち着かない
to be unsettled
- そわそわしている
to be fidgety
- ^き ^お ^つ 気が落ち着かない
to feel restless

Adjusted Expression

^お ^つ 落ち着かない

to feel unsettled

Example

A 「試験^{しけん}の前^{まえ}でそわそわしてるね」 B 「うん、緊張^{きんちょう}して落ち着^おかないよ」

A: You're restless before the exam, aren't you? B: Yeah, I'm nervous and can't settle down.

Notes

"Sowasowa suru" is a colloquial expression used when someone feels restless because of anxiety, nervousness, or anticipation. In this example, B is nervous before the exam and cannot settle down. The expression is

not limited to negative anxiety; it can also be used when someone is excited or waiting for something pleasant. It often suggests that the body or mind cannot stay still because the feeling has already moved ahead.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

anxiety

nervousness

anticipation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

anxiety

nervousness

anticipation

Small details / Trivial things

こま
細かいこと

Komakai koto

small details / trivial things

Variants

- ^{さいぶ}細部のこと
small details
- ^{ちい}小さなこと
minor things
- ^{ささい}些細なこと
trivial matters
- ^{じゅうばこ すみ}重箱の隅をつつく
to nitpick

Adjusted Expression

^{ささい}些細なこと

a trivial matter

Example

A 「^{かみ}髪、ちゃんと^{むす}結んで^い行きなさい」 B 「そんな^{こま}細かいこと」

A: Make sure to tie your hair properly. B: Why worry about such a small thing?

Notes

"Komakai koto" refers to small details or minor matters, but in conversation it can also be used to brush off someone's correction or warning. In this example, B responds to being told to tie their hair properly by saying "sonna komakai koto," treating the warning as something not worth worrying about. It does not simply mean "detailed matters"; it can carry resistance or downplaying, as in "You don't have to worry about such a small thing." In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "sasai na koto" (a trivial matter) or "saibu no mondai" (a matter of detail).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation

resistance

downplaying

response to correction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

reaction expression

downplaying

resistance

Messy / Disorganized

ごちゃごちゃ

Gocha gocha

messy / disorganized

Variants

- ^ち散らかっている

cluttered

- ^{らんざつ}乱雑な

disorderly

- ^{せいり}整理されていない

not organized

- ^{こんらん}混乱した

chaotic

Adjusted Expression

^ち散らかっています。

It is cluttered.

Example

A 「^{へや}部屋、ごちゃごちゃしてるね」 B 「うん、^{かたづ}片付けないと」

A: Your room is messy, isn't it? B: Yeah, I need to tidy up.

Notes

"Gocha gocha" is a colloquial expression used when things are messy, cluttered, or not organized. In this example, A looks at the room and says "gocha gocha shiteru ne," meaning that the room is messy. It can describe not only physical clutter, but also explanations, conversations, schedules, or relationships that feel confused or poorly organized. It is basically a state description, but depending on the situation it can also carry mild dissatisfaction or evaluation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is cluttered" or "It is not organized."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

state description

evaluation

emotional expression

pointing out lack of organization

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

state description

evaluation

lack of organization

To be anxious and impatient

やきもきする

Yakimoki suru

to be anxious and impatient

Variants

- やきもきしている
to be anxiously waiting
- 気^きをもむ
to worry anxiously
- もどかしい
to feel frustrated
- じれったい
to feel impatient
- いらいらする
to feel irritated

Adjusted Expression

気^きをもんでいます。

I am waiting anxiously.

Example

A 「連絡^{れんらく}、まだ来^こないね」 B 「うん、やきもきする」

A: They still haven't contacted us. B: Yeah, I'm getting anxious waiting.

Notes

"Yakimoki suru" is a colloquial expression used when the speaker feels anxious and impatient while waiting for a result, reply, or development. In this example, B reacts to the fact that no contact has come yet by saying "yakimoki suru." It is not simply anger; it includes the feeling of being kept waiting without knowing what will happen, and wanting the situation to become clear soon. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I am waiting anxiously" or "I am feeling concerned."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

anxiety

impatience

reaction to waiting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

anxiety

impatience

waiting response

Waste / Futility

む だ
無駄

Muda

waste / futility

Variants

• ^{む い み}無意味

meaningless

• ^{む え き}無益

pointless

• ^{と ろ う}徒労

futile

• ^{じ か ん}時間^{む だ}の無駄

a waste of time

Adjusted Expression

^{ゆう え き}有益ではありません。

It is not useful.

Example

A 「この仕事、^{む だ}無駄じゃない？」 B 「うん、^{じ か ん}時間^{む だ}の無駄だよね」

A: Isn't this work a waste? B: Yeah, it's a waste of time.

Notes

"Muda" is used when the speaker feels that the time or effort spent on something does not lead to a meaningful or worthwhile result. In this example, A and B judge the work as having little value and call it "muda" or "jikan no muda" (a waste of time). It does not simply mean that the result is small; it can also carry a sense of futility, as if continuing would not be worth the effort. When directed at someone's action, it can sound like a strong negative evaluation, so it should be used with care. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is not useful" or "It is unlikely to be effective."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

negation

emotional expression

sense of futility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

negation

sense of futility

To be irritated / To be annoyed

いらいら
イライラする

Iraira suru

to be irritated / to be annoyed

Variants

• ^{いらだ}苛立つ

to be frustrated

• ^{はらだ}腹立たしい

to be irritated

• ^{ふかい}不快に ^{かん}感じる

to feel uncomfortable

• ^き気にさわる

to get on one's nerves

Adjusted Expression

^{いらだ}苛立っています。

I feel irritated.

Example

A 「なかなか^{れんらく}連絡が^こ来ないね」 B 「うん、^{いらいら}イライラする」

A: They still haven't contacted us. B: Yeah, I'm getting irritated.

Notes

"Iraira suru" is a colloquial expression used when the speaker feels irritated or annoyed because things are not going as expected or because someone's response is slow. In this example, B reacts to the fact that no contact has come yet by saying "iraira suru." Compared with No.571 "yakimoki suru," which includes anxious waiting and impatience, "iraira suru" more strongly expresses dissatisfaction toward the person or situation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I feel irritated" or "I feel uncomfortable."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

dissatisfaction

anger

irritation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

dissatisfaction

irritation

To be tense / To be on edge

ぴりぴり
ピリピリしてる

Piripiri shiteru

to be tense / to be on edge

Variants

- ^{きんちょう}緊張している

to be tense

- ^{いらいら}イライラしている

to be irritated

- ^{しんけいしつ}神経質になっている

to be on edge

- ^{くうきは}空気が張りつめている

the atmosphere is tense

Adjusted Expression

^{きんちょう}緊張しています。

It is tense.

Example

A 「^{しけん}試験の^{まえ}前で^{ぴりぴり}ピリピリしてるね」 B 「うん、^{きんちょう}緊張して^お落ち^つ着かないよ」

A: You're on edge before the exam, aren't you? B: Yeah, I'm nervous and can't settle down.

Notes

"Piripiri shiteru" is a colloquial expression used when a person or atmosphere feels tense because of nervousness, anxiety, or irritation. In this example, B is tense before the exam and cannot settle down. Compared with No.568 "sowasowa suru," which suggests restless movement, "piripiri shiteru" suggests that the nerves are tight and ready to react even to small stimuli. It can describe not only a person but also the atmosphere of a place, as in "the workplace feels tense." In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I am tense" or "The atmosphere is tense."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

tension

anxiety

describing the atmosphere

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

tension

atmosphere

mimetic word

Moving around

うご まわ
動き回ってて

Ugoki mawattete

moving around

Variants

- ^{うご まわ}動き回っている
moving around
- ^{はし まわ}走り回っている
running around
- ^{ある まわ}歩き回っている
walking around
- ^{うご}あちこち動いている
moving here and there

Adjusted Expression

^{うご まわ}動き回っていました。

It was moving around.

Example

A 「ねえ、^{ぱん だ}パンダ、どうだった？」 B 「うん、^{うご まわ}動き回ってて^{かわい}可愛かったよ」

A: Hey, how was the panda? B: Yeah, it was moving around and was cute.

Notes

"Ugoki mawattete" is a casual form of "ugoki mawatte ite," used to describe someone or an animal moving around here and there while also sharing the speaker's impression. In this example, B says that the panda was not just sitting still, but was moving around, and that this made it look cute. "Ugoki mawaru" does not simply mean to move; it suggests active movement around within a certain place or area. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "ugoki mawatte imashita" (it was moving around) or "kappatsu ni ugoite imashita" (it was moving actively).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

action description

state explanation

sharing an impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

action description

state explanation

sharing an impression

...or something like that

とかなんとか

Toka nantoka

...or something like that

Variants

- ...とかなんとか
...or something like that
- ...とかなんとかって
...or whatever
- ...とかなんとかいう
something about ...
- ...とかそんな話^{はなし}
...or some such thing

Adjusted Expression

などということでした。

It was something like that.

Example

A 「昨日^{きのう}の会議^{かいぎ}、どうだった？」 B 「うん、消費税^{しょうひぜい}とかなんとかって^{はなし}いう話^{はなし}だったよ」

A: How was the meeting yesterday? B: Yeah, it was something about consumption tax or something.

Notes

"Toka nantoka" is a spoken expression used to report something vaguely without stating the content precisely. In this example, B does not explain the meeting in detail, but says "shouhizei toka nantoka tte iu hanashi datta yo," meaning that it was something about consumption tax or something like that. Here, "nantoka" does not mean "somehow" or "by some means"; together with "toka," it works to blur or soften the reported content. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It was something like that" or "It was about"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

vague reference

ambiguous reporting

uncertain quotation

unclear memory

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

vague expression

softening content

quotation

Messy / Chaotic / Extremely

めちゃくちゃ

Mechakucha

messy / chaotic / extremely

Variants

- ^{こんらん}混乱した
confused
- ^{むちつじょ}無秩序な
disorderly
- めちゃめちゃな
chaotic
- めちゃくちゃ^{さむい}寒い
extremely cold
- めちゃくちゃおいしい
really delicious

Adjusted Expression

^{ひじょう}非常に / ^{こんらん}混乱している

very / chaotic

Example

A 「^{へや}部屋、めちゃくちゃだね」 B 「うん、^{かたづ}片付けないと」

A: Your room is a total mess, isn't it? B: Yeah, I need to tidy up.

Notes

"Mechakucha" is a colloquial expression used when things or situations are badly disordered or chaotic. In this example, A sees that the room is very messy and says "mechakucha da ne." Compared with No.570 "gocha gocha," which suggests that many things are cluttered or not organized, "mechakucha" gives a stronger evaluation that the situation is badly out of order or far from normal. It is also used adverbially to emphasize degree, as in "mechakucha samui" (extremely cold) or "mechakucha oishii" (really delicious). In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "very," "extremely," or "It is chaotic."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

state description

evaluation

emotional expression

emphasis

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

state description

evaluation

emphasis

degree expression

Too much / Too ...

...すぎ

...sugi

too much / too ...

Variants

- ^{はたら}働きすぎ
working too much
- やりすぎ
overdoing it
- ^た食べすぎ
eating too much
- ^い言いすぎ
saying too much
- ^{かんが}考えすぎ
thinking too much

Adjusted Expression

^{かじょう}過剰です。

It is excessive.

Example

A ^{かれ}「彼、^{しごと}仕事し^す過ぎだよ」 B 「うん、やりすぎ」

A: He's working too much. B: Yeah, he's overdoing it.

Notes

"...sugi" is used when an action or state is felt to go beyond an appropriate limit. In this example, A worries that he is working too much, and B agrees by saying "yarisugi" (he is overdoing it). It attaches to forms such as the continuative form of verbs, as in "tabesugi" (eating too much), "iisugi" (saying too much), and "kangaesugi" (thinking too much). It is not just a description of quantity; it can also carry evaluation or warning that something has gone too far. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is excessive" or "It goes beyond an appropriate limit."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

warning

emotional expression

exceeding a limit

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

warning

degree expression

exceeding a limit

As long as it works

つか
使えればいい

Tsukaereba ii

as long as it works / as long as it can be used

Variants

- ^{うご}動けばいい
as long as it works
- ^{つか}使えればいい
as long as it can be used
- ^{さいていげんつか}最低限使えればいい
as long as it is minimally usable
- ^{つか}とりあえず使えればいい
as long as it works for now

Adjusted Expression

^{しょう}使用できれば良^よいです。

It is acceptable as long as it can be used.

Example

A 「このソフト、どう？」 B 「あまり良^よくない。使^{つか}えればいいとか、動^{うご}けばいいっていうんじゃない、使^{つか}いやすいかどうかなんだよ」

A: How's this software? B: It's not very good. It isn't just about whether it can be used or whether it works. What matters is whether it's easy to use.

Notes

"Tsukaereba ii" expresses the idea that it is enough if the minimum condition is met. In this example, B says that merely being usable or working is not enough; what matters is whether the software is easy to use. In other words, "tsukaereba ii" can express compromise or a minimum standard, but depending on the context it can also be used critically to point out that the standard is too low. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is acceptable as long as it can be used" or "It is acceptable if it is minimally usable."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

condition setting

compromise

limited requirement

minimum condition

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

condition setting

compromise

minimum condition

evaluation

In the first place / To begin with

そもそも

Somosomo

in the first place / to begin with

Variants

- ^{さいしょ}最初から
from the beginning
- ^{もともと}元々
originally
- ^{こんぽんてき}根本的に
fundamentally
- ^{はなし}そもそもの話
the whole point from the start

Adjusted Expression

^{こんぽんてき}根本的には、

fundamentally,

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼は^{しごと}仕事が^{おそ}遅いよね」 B 「うん、^{じかん}そもそも^る時間に^{はず}ルーズなんだよ」

A: He's slow at work, isn't he? B: Yeah, to begin with, he's not punctual.

Notes

"Somosomo" is used when the speaker moves the discussion from a surface-level issue back to a more fundamental cause or premise. In this example, B responds to the specific problem that he is slow at work by saying "somosomo jikan ni ruuzu nan da yo," shifting the explanation to his basic lack of punctuality. It does not merely indicate the beginning of something; it can also carry a critical nuance, suggesting that the matter should be reconsidered from that starting point. For this reason, it can sound somewhat strong in conversation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "fundamentally" or "originally."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking the premise

presenting the root cause

reframing the discussion

criticism

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

checking the premise

cause presentation

reframing the discussion

criticism

I'll take this / I'll go with this

これにする

Kore ni suru

I'll take this / I'll go with this

Variants

- これにする
I'll take this
- これに^き決める
I'll decide on this
- これを^{えら}選ぶ
I'll choose this
- これを^{たの}頼む
I'll order this

Adjusted Expression

これを^{えら}選びます。

I will choose this.

Example

A 「何^{なに}にする？」 B 「うん、これにする」

A: What will you have? B: I'll go with this.

Notes

"Kore ni suru" is a spoken expression used when choosing one option from several and showing one's decision on the spot. In this example, B is asked "What will you have?" and answers "kore ni suru," deciding on that option. It is more conversational than "kore o erabu" (I will choose this), and is natural when choosing food, an item, a method, or a plan in front of you. However, in a situation where others may also want the same thing, saying "kore ni suru" too quickly can sound as if the speaker is pushing their own choice forward. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "kore o erabimasu" or "kochira ni shimasu" (I will choose this one).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

selection

expression of intention

decision

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

selection

expression of intention

decision

It's my turn

わたし ばん
私の番

Watashi no ban

It's my turn

Variants

- わたし ばん
私の番

It's my turn

- つぎ わたし
次は私

I'm next

- きみ ばん
君の番

It's your turn

- だれ ばん
誰の番？

Whose turn is it?

Adjusted Expression

わたし じゅんばん
私の順番です。

It is my turn.

Example

A 「つぎ だれ
次は誰？」 B 「わたし ばん
私の番」

A: Who's next? B: It's my turn.

Notes

"Watashi no ban" is a spoken response used to show that one's turn has come. In this example, A asks "Who's next?" and B answers "watashi no ban" (It's my turn). Here, "ban" does not simply mean a number; it refers to one's place in an order where someone is expected to act. It is natural in situations such as games, presentations, tasks, or waiting lines where people need to know who goes next. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "watashi no junban desu" (It is my turn).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking the turn

expressing order

signaling participation

response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

turn expression

response

participation

That's too much / That's unfair

あんまりだ

Anmari da

That's too much / That's unfair

Variants

- それはあんまりだ
That's too much
- そりゃ、あんまりだよ
That's really unfair
- ひど酷い
That's terrible
- ふこうへい不公平だ
That's unfair
- ふとう不当だ
That's unjust

Adjusted Expression

う受け入れがたいじょうきょう状況です。

That is difficult to accept.

Example

A 「せんせい先生、あす明日、きゅう急にしけん試験するって」 B 「うん、そりゃ、あんまりだよ」

A: The teacher said there will suddenly be an exam tomorrow. B: Yeah, that's really unfair.

Notes

"Anmari da" is a colloquial expression used when the speaker feels that someone's action or a situation is too harsh, unfair, or difficult to accept. In this example, B reacts to the sudden announcement of an exam tomorrow by saying "sorya, anmari da yo." It is stronger than simply saying that something is not good; it expresses that the speaker finds the situation unreasonable or unfair. When said directly to someone, it can sound like a protest, so it should be used with care. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That is difficult to accept" or "I think it is unfair."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

negation

emotional expression

sense of unfairness

protest

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

negation

protest

sense of unfairness

I need to talk to you

はなし
話がある

Hanashi ga aru

I need to talk to you / I have something to talk about

Variants

- そうだん 相談がある

I have something to ask you about

- ようじ 用事がある

I have something to take care of with you

- つた 伝えたいことがある

I have something to tell you

- はなし ちょっと話がある

I need to talk to you for a moment

Adjusted Expression

そうだん 相談したいことがあります。

There is something I would like to discuss with you.

Example

A 「はなし ちょっと話があるんだけど、いま 今いい？」 B 「うん、どうしたの？」

A: I need to talk to you for a moment. Is now okay? B: Yeah, what's up?

Notes

"Hanashi ga aru" is used when the speaker has something to tell or discuss with the listener. In this example, A says "chotto hanashi ga aru n dakedo, ima ii?" and starts the conversation while checking whether the listener is available. By itself, "hanashi ga aru" can sound somewhat serious and may make the listener brace for something important. For this reason, in everyday conversation it is often softened with expressions such as "chotto" and "n dakedo," making it easier for the listener to receive. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "There is something I would like to discuss with you" or "There is something I would like to talk about."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

conversation opening

expression of intention

consultation

signaling an important topic

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

conversation opening

expression of intention

consultation

preface

It's not worth pushing yourself that far

むり
無理してまでやるほどのことじゃない

Muri shite made yaru hodo no koto janai

It's not worth pushing yourself that far

Variants

- そこまで頑張ることじゃない
It's not worth trying that hard
- そんなに無理することじゃない
It's not necessary to push yourself that much
- 無理してまでやることじゃない
It's not worth doing if you have to overdo it
- そこまでしてやるほどのことじゃない
It's not worth going that far

Adjusted Expression

むり おこな ひつよう
無理をしてまで行う必要はありません。

There is no need to overdo it to that extent.

Example

A 「試験のために徹夜で勉強するよ」 B 「いや、無理してまでやるほどのこと
じゃないよ。ちゃんと休んだほうが良いよ」

A: I'm going to study all night for the exam. B: No, it's not worth pushing yourself that far. You should get proper rest.

Notes

"Muri shite made yaru hodo no koto janai" is a spoken expression used when someone is about to push themselves too hard and the speaker wants to say that it is not necessary to go that far. In this example, B tells A, who is planning to study all night, that it is not worth overdoing it and that they should rest properly. "Hodo no koto janai" means that the action is not important or valuable enough to justify that much effort. It is often used not to blame the person, but to advise them not to overdo it. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "There is no need to overdo it to that extent."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation

advice

stopping someone

discouraging excessive effort

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

advice

stopping someone

discouraging overexertion

Looks kind of fun

なん たの
何か楽しそう

Nanka tanoshisou

looks kind of fun / seems fun

Variants

- ^{なん おもしろ}何か面白そう
looks kind of interesting
- ^{なん たの}何か楽しそう
looks kind of fun
- ^{なん わくわく}何かワクワクする
somehow exciting
- ^{なん}何かよさそう
looks kind of good

Adjusted Expression

^{たの}楽しそうです。

It seems fun.

Example

A 「^{あたら}新しいゲーム、^{げーむ おもしろ}面白そうだね」 B 「うん、^{なん たの}何か楽しそう」

A: The new game looks interesting, doesn't it? B: Yeah, it looks kind of fun.

Notes

"Nanka tanoshisou" is a spoken expression used when something looks fun based on the speaker's immediate impression, even before they can clearly explain why. In this example, B looks at the new game and reacts with "nanka tanoshisou." The word "nanka" softens the statement and suggests that the impression comes from the overall feeling rather than a precise reason. It is more casual than "tanoshisou desu" and gives a spontaneous evaluation in conversation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It seems fun" or "It seems interesting."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emotional expression

evaluation

prediction

impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotional expression

evaluation

impression expression

softening

It's not like that / That's not what I mean

そういうことじゃない

Sou iu koto janai

it's not like that / that's not what I mean

Variants

- そういうことじゃないよ
It's not like that
- そうい^い意味^みじゃない
That's not what I mean
- そうい^は話^{なし}じゃない
That's not the point
- 違^{ちが}うよ、そういうことじゃない
No, that's not it

Adjusted Expression

そういう意味^{いみ}ではありません。

That is not what I mean.

Example

A 「私^{わたし}が悪^{わる}かったんだ」 B 「いや、そういうことじゃないよ。君^{きみ}のせいじゃないよ」

A: It was my fault. B: No, it's not like that. It's not your fault.

Notes

"Sou iu koto janai" is a spoken expression used when the listener's interpretation is off and the speaker wants to redirect it. In this example, A interprets the situation as their own fault, but B stops that interpretation by saying "sou iu koto janai yo." The expression does not simply deny a fact; it says that the point of the matter is not in that direction. It can be used to stop a misunderstanding without blaming the other person, but depending on tone, it can also sound like a strong rejection. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That is not what I mean" or "That is not the intended meaning."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negation

correction

repairing a misunderstanding

redirecting interpretation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negation

correction

repairing misunderstanding

adjusting interpretation

I was wondering if...

～かなと思^{おも}って。

~kana to omotte.

I was wondering if...

Variants

- ～かなと思^{おも}って
I was wondering if...
- ～かなと思^{おも}いまして
I was thinking that maybe...
- ～かもと思^{おも}って
I thought it might be...
- ～かな^{おも}って思^{おも}って
I was kind of thinking...

Adjusted Expression

～かもしれないと思^{おも}いまして。

I thought it might be...

Example

A 「明日、雨^{あした あめ ふ}が降^おるかなと思^{おも}って...」 B 「そうだね、たぶん」

A: I was wondering if it might rain tomorrow... B: Yeah, probably.

Notes

"~kana to omotte" is a spoken expression used when the speaker gently brings up something they are wondering or worried about without stating it firmly. In this example, A says "ashita, ame ga furu kana to omotte..." and uses the possibility of rain as an entry point for continuing the conversation. "Kana" adds uncertainty, and "to omotte" presents it as the speaker's own thought. By leaving the sentence unfinished, the speaker leaves room for consultation, suggestion, or confirmation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "~kamoshirenai to omoimashite" (I thought it might be...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of doubt

preface to consultation

prelude to suggestion

trailing off

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of doubt

preface to consultation

prelude to suggestion

incomplete sentence

I'm telling you, this is true

これ、^{ほんとう} ^{はなし} 本当の話

Kore, hontou no hanashi

I'm telling you, this is true / This is a true story

Variants

- これ、^{ほんとう} ^{はなし} 本当の話

I'm telling you, this is true

- これ、^{ほんとう} 本当なんだよ

This is really true

- ^{うそ} 嘘じゃないよ

I'm not making this up

- ^{ほんとう} ^{はなし} 本当にあった話

This really happened

Adjusted Expression

これは^{ほんとう} ^{はなし} 本当の話です。

This is a true story.

Example

A 「たったの30分で^{ぶん} ^{ぜんぶ} 全部、^{おぼ} 覚えたんだって。これ、^{ほんとう} ^{はなし} 本当の話」 B 「えっ、^{ほん} ^と ホント？」

A: I heard he memorized everything in just 30 minutes. I'm telling you, this is true. B: Really?

Notes

"Kore, hontou no hanashi" is a spoken expression used when the speaker tells something surprising and emphasizes that it is true, not made up. In this example, A says that someone memorized everything in just 30 minutes, then adds "kore, hontou no hanashi" to assure the listener that it really happened. It is not just a plain statement of fact; it anticipates the listener's surprise and means something like "This may be hard to believe, but it is true." In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "This is a true story" or "This actually happened."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis

assuring truth

sharing surprise

information provision

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emphasis

assuring truth

sharing surprise

That's what I keep telling him, though

そう^い言^いって^いる^いん^いで^いす^いけ^いど^いね

Sou itteru n desu kedo ne

that's what I keep telling him, though / I've been telling him that, but...

Variants

- そう^い言^いって^いる^いん^いで^いす^いけ^いど^いね
That's what I keep telling him, though
- そう^{つた}伝^{つた}えて^{つた}る^{つた}ん^{つた}で^{つた}す^{つた}け^{つた}ど^{つた}ね
I've been telling him that, but...
- そう^{せつめい}説^{せつめい}明^{せつめい}して^{せつめい}る^{せつめい}ん^{せつめい}で^{せつめい}す^{せつめい}け^{せつめい}ど^{せつめい}ね
I've been explaining that, but...
- い^いつ^いも^いそ^いう^い言^いって^いる^いん^いで^いす^いけ^いど^いね
I always tell him that, though

Adjusted Expression

そ^{つた}の^{つた}よ^{つた}う^{つた}に^{つた}伝^{つた}え^{つた}て^{つた}い^{つた}ま^{つた}す^{つた}が^{つた}、...

I have been telling him that, but...

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼^{かれ}、^{ちこく}また^{ちこく}遅^{ちこく}刻^{ちこく}？」 B 「^{うん}う^{ちこく}ん^{ちこく}、^{ちこく}遅^{ちこく}刻^{ちこく}し^{ちこく}ち^{ちこく}ゃ^{ちこく}だ^{ちこく}め^{ちこく}だ^{ちこく}よ^{ちこく}っ^{ちこく}て^{ちこく}、^いい^つも^い、^いそ^いう^い言^いっ^いて^いる^いん^いで^いす^いけ^いど^いね」

A: Is he late again? B: Yeah. I always tell him he shouldn't be late, though...

Notes

"Sou itteru n desu kedo ne" is a spoken expression used when the speaker has been telling someone something repeatedly, but the situation has not changed. In this example, B says that they always tell him not to be late, but he is late again. If the speaker only said "sou itteru," it would simply report what they say. By ending with "n desu kedo ne," the expression leaves a sense of trouble or resignation: the speaker has been saying it, but it is not working. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I have been telling him that, but there has been no improvement."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation

sense of trouble

resignation

repeated effort

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

explanation

sense of trouble

resignation

trailing off

That's all / Only that much

それだけ

Sore dake

that's all / only that much

Variants

- それだけです
That's all there is
- それだけしかない
There is only that much
- それだけで十分^{じゅうぶん}
That alone is enough
- 重要な^{じゅうよう}のはそれだけ
That's the only important thing

Adjusted Expression

それだけです。

That's all.

Example

A 「今日の会議^{きょう かいぎ}、どうだった？」 B 「うん、重要な^{じゅうよう はなし}話はそれだけ」

A: How was today's meeting? B: Yeah, that's all the important stuff.

Notes

"Sore dake" is used to limit the matter under discussion to just one thing. In this example, B says that this was the only important point in the meeting, organizing the main point by narrowing it down. It can mean that the limited amount is enough, as in "sore dake de juubun" (that alone is enough), or that there is not enough, as in "sore dake shika nai" (there is only that much). In conversation, it works as an immediate expression for sorting out what matters and what does not. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That's all" or "That is the only important point."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

limitation

emphasis

conclusion

organizing the point

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

limitation

emphasis

organizing the point

I'd like to try it

やってみたいなあ

Yatte mitai naa

I'd like to try it / I want to try it

Variants

- やってみたいなあ

I'd like to try it

- ^{いちど}一度やってみたいなあ

I'd like to try it once

- ^い行ってみたいなあ

I'd like to go there

- ^{けいけん}経験してみたいなあ

I'd like to experience it

Adjusted Expression

やってみたい^{おも}と思います。

I would like to try it.

Example

A 「スカイダイビング^{すか}って^い楽しい^だらしいよ」 B 「うん、^{いちど}一度、やってみたいなあ」

A: I heard skydiving is fun. B: Yeah, I'd like to try it once.

Notes

"Yatte mitai naa" is a spoken expression used when the speaker wants to try or experience something they have not done before. In this example, B hears about skydiving and says "ichido, yatte mitai naa," expressing a wish to try it once. "~te mitai" expresses the desire to try something, and "naa" leaves a lingering feeling of hope or longing that arises in the moment. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I would like to try it" or "I would like to experience it once."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of desire

expression of hope

emotional expression

interest in experience

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of desire

expression of hope

interest in experience

It is good, though...

おいしいけれども...

Oishii keredomo...

It is good, though...

Variants

- おいしいけど...
It is good, but...
- おいしいけれども...
It is good, though...
- いいんだけど...
It is fine, but...
- ^{わる}悪くはないけれども...
It is not bad, but...

Adjusted Expression

おいしいですが、別の問題もあります。

It is good, but there are other issues.

Example

A ^{あた}「^ら新しいレストラン、おいしいよ」 B 「^{たか}でも、高いんだよね。おいしいけれども...」

A: The new restaurant is good. B: But it is expensive, you know. It is good, though...

Notes

"Oishii keredomo..." is used when the speaker acknowledges a positive point but leaves room for hesitation or disagreement. In this example, B admits that the new restaurant is good, but because it is expensive, they stop at "oishii keredomo..." without completing the sentence. By leaving the part after "keredomo" unstated, the speaker implies something like "but that is not enough to decide" or "there are other concerns."

Compared with "kedo," "keredomo" sounds slightly more formal. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is good, but there are other issues."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

contrast

concession

trailing off

implication

holding back evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

slightly formal expression

contrast

concession

trailing off

incomplete sentence

Nothing beats...

かぎ
～に限る

~ni kagiru

nothing beats... / ...is the best

Variants

- ～^{かぎ}に限る
nothing beats...
- ～^{いちばん}が一番だ
...is the best
- ～^{いちばん}が一番良い
...is the best choice
- ～^きに決まっている
it has to be...

Adjusted Expression

いちばんよ
～が一番良いです。

...is the best.

Example

A 「夏^{なつ}の暑^{あつ}いとき、何^{なに}が^{いちばん}一番？」 B 「やっぱり、冷^{つめ}たい飲^のみ物^{もの}に限^{かぎ}るよね」

A: What's best on a hot summer day? B: Nothing beats a cold drink.

Notes

"~ni kagiru" is used to say that something is the best choice in a certain situation, or that nothing beats it. In this example, B says "tsumetai nomimono ni kagiru yo ne," meaning that on a hot summer day, a cold drink is the best. It does not merely limit the choice; it also expresses preference and a sense of conviction based on experience. When used with "yappari," it gives the feeling that, after all is considered, this is the best option. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "...is the best" or "...is optimal."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

limitation emphasis evaluation expressing preference

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language limitation emphasis evaluation preference

If I had to say yes or no

あり なし
アリかナシかでいえば

Ari ka nashi ka de ieba

if I had to say yes or no

Variants

- ^{あり} ^{なし}
アリかナシかでいえば
if I had to say yes or no
- ^{あり} ^{なし}
アリかナシかっていえば
if I had to choose between yes and no
- ^{あり} ^よ
アリ寄り
leaning yes
- ^{あり}
まあアリかな
I'd say it's acceptable
- ^{なし}
ナシではないかな
I wouldn't say no

Adjusted Expression

^{さんせい} ^{はんたい} ^の
賛成か反対かをはっきり述べるならば、

if I had to state clearly whether I agree or disagree,

Example

A 「この案、^{あん} ^{あり} ^{なし} ^のアリかナシかでいえば？」 B 「うーん、^{あり} ^{なし} ^のアリかナシかっていえば、
^{あり}アリかな」

A: So, for this idea, if you had to say yes or no? B: Hmm... if I had to choose, I'd say yes.

Notes

"Ari ka nashi ka de ieba" is used when the speaker frames an idea or action as a simple choice between whether it is acceptable or not before giving a detailed evaluation. In this example, B is not strongly supporting the idea, but by saying "ari kana," the speaker gives weak or tentative approval. "Ari" means acceptable, while "nashi" means not acceptable. However, the expression does not always lead to a positive answer; a speaker can also say "nashi kana." The important point is that it allows the speaker to give an immediate evaluation within the short frame of "yes / no" before explaining the reasons in detail. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "if I had to state clearly whether I agree or disagree" or "if we judge whether it is acceptable or not."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

immediate evaluation

framing as a binary choice

weak approval

omission of reasons

holding back evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

evaluation

soft positive

pragmatics

framing

To go somewhere to do something

～し^いに行く

~shi ni iku

to go somewhere to do something

Variants

- 見^みに行^いく
to go to see something
- 買^かいに行^いく
to go to buy something
- 食^たべに行^いく
to go to eat something
- 遊^{あそ}びに行^いく
to go to play / hang out

Adjusted Expression

～する^いために行きます。

to go in order to do something

Example

A 「新^{あたら}しい映^{えい}画^が、見^みに行^いく？」 B 「うん、行^いこう」

A: Shall we go see the new movie? B: Yeah, let's go.

Notes

"~shi ni iku" is used when someone goes somewhere for the purpose of doing something. In this example, A says "atarashii eiga, mi ni iku?" and asks whether they should go out together to see the new movie. It appears in expressions such as "mi ni iku" (go to see), "kai ni iku" (go to buy), "tabe ni iku" (go to eat), and "asobi ni iku" (go to play or hang out). In conversation, "mi ni iku?" by itself can function as an invitation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "to go in order to do something." In fast speech, forms such as "mi ni iku" or "kai ni iku" may sound smoothly connected, but in writing they are normally kept separate.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of purpose

expression of action

expression of movement

invitation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

purpose expression

action expression

movement expression

invitation

Are you free? / Is it available?

あ
空^あいてる

Aiteru

are you free? / is it available?

Variants

- その日^ひ、空^あいてる？
Are you free that day?
- 席^{せき}、空^あいてる？
Is this seat available?
- 部屋^{へや}、空^あいてる？
Is the room available?
- 時間^{じかん}、空^あいてる？
Do you have time?

Adjusted Expression

あ
空^あいていますか。

Are you available? / Is it available?

Example

A 「その日^ひ、空^あいてる？」 B 「うん、何^{なに}？」 A 「映画^{えいが}、見^みに行^いこ」

A: Are you free that day? B: Yeah, what is it? A: Let's go see a movie.

Notes

"Aiteru" is a colloquial expression used to ask whether a time, seat, room, or place is available. In this example, A asks "sono hi, aiteru?" to check whether the listener is free before inviting them to a movie. When used about time, it means that the person has no plans. When used about a seat or room, it means that it is not being used and is available. Asking "aiteru?" before making an invitation makes it easier for the listener to respond than stating the invitation immediately. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "Is it available?" or "Would that time be convenient for you?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of state

question

confirmation

preface to invitation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

state expression

question

confirmation

preface to invitation

To be forced to give up without recourse

泣き寝入り

Nakineiri

being forced to give up without recourse

Variants

- 泣き寝入りする
to be forced to give up
- 泣く泣くあきらめる
to give up reluctantly
- 仕方なくあきらめる
to have no choice but to give up
- 不当だが受け入れるしかない
to accept it even though it is unfair

Adjusted Expression

不当だと思いながらも、受け入れるしかありません。

One has no choice but to accept it, even though it feels unfair.

Example

A 「問い合わせても結局『仕様です』で終わっちゃった」 B 「それって泣き寝入りだよね」

A: Even after I asked about it, it just ended with, 'That's how it works.' B: That's basically being forced to give up, isn't it?

Notes

"Nakineiri" is an idiomatic expression used when someone feels that something is unfair but has no effective way to protest, recover the loss, or change the situation, and therefore has no choice but to give up. In this example, A asked about the problem, but the response ended with "That's how it works," leaving no real way forward. B calls this "nakineiri," expressing the frustration of having to accept something even though it feels unfair. It is not simply enduring quietly; the central feeling is unfairness combined with having no recourse. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "One has no choice but to accept it, even though it feels unfair."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation of unfairness

resignation

having no recourse

inner frustration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

idiom

unfairness

resignation

frustration

Long-lasting / Durable

ながも
長持ち

Nagamochi

long-lasting / durable

Variants

- ^{ながも}長持ちする
to last a long time
- ^{なが} ^{つか}長く使える
can be used for a long time
- ^も持ちがいい
lasts well
- ^{じょうぶ}丈夫な
sturdy
- ^{たいきゅう} ^{たか}耐久性が高い
highly durable

Adjusted Expression

^{たいきゅう} ^{たか}耐久性が高いです。

It is highly durable.

Example

A 「この靴、^{くつ} ^{ながも}長持ちすんの？」 B 「うん、^{ねん} ^も3年は持つよ」

A: Do these shoes last long? B: Yeah, they'll last at least three years.

Notes

"Nagamochi" is used when an object or product can be used for a long time. In this example, A asks whether the shoes will last, checking whether they will avoid wearing out or breaking quickly. "Nagamochi suru" does not simply describe length of time; it can also be used when judging whether something is worth buying or whether its quality is good. In "san-nen wa motsu yo" (they'll last at least three years), "motsu" does not mean "to have"; it means that the usable condition continues. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is highly durable" or "It can be used for a long period of time."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of durability

emphasis on quality

expression of endurance

purchase judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

durability expression

quality emphasis

evaluation

Pretty interesting / Quite interesting

けっこうおもしろ
結構面白い

Kekkoo omoshiroi

pretty interesting / quite interesting

Variants

- けっこうおもしろ面白い
pretty interesting
- かなりおもしろ面白い
quite interesting
- なかなかおもしろ面白い
rather interesting
- おも思ったよりおもしろ面白い
more interesting than I expected

Adjusted Expression

よそう予想よりもおもしろ面白いです。

It is more interesting than expected.

Example

A 「この本、結構面白いよ」 B 「へえ、読んでみようかな」

A: This book is pretty interesting. B: Oh, maybe I'll give it a read.

Notes

"Kekkoo omoshiroi" is a spoken expression used when something is more interesting than expected or interesting enough to be worth noting. In this example, A says that the book is "kekkoo omoshiroi," giving a positive evaluation that makes B consider reading it. It is not as strong as saying "very interesting"; rather, it gives a slightly restrained but positive judgment. "Kekkoo" can suggest that something is better than expected or surprisingly not bad. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is more interesting than expected" or "It is sufficiently interesting."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis on evaluation

expression of interest

positive opinion

evaluation above expectation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emphasis on evaluation

expression of interest

above expectation

Colophon

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